

**LIVED EXPERIENCES OF STUDENT ENTREPRENEURS IN
SANTA ROSA SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY HIGH SCHOOL**

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DEDICATION

This research paper is lovingly dedicated to our dear parents who have continuously supported and encouraged us throughout our journey. They have given us the drive and resolve to persevere in spite of the many hardships we faced. Without their unwavering love and support, we would not have been able to complete this study.

We also dedicate this research paper to our family members, friends, and classmates who have shared this journey with us. Your willingness to listen to our troubles and provide advice has greatly helped us stay motivated throughout this study.

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— The Researchers

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of five student entrepreneurs at Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School, examining their motivations, challenges, coping strategies, and ethical considerations. Semi-structured interviews revealed eight themes: Financial Empowerment and Autonomy, Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management, Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship, Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations, Operational Challenges and Competence Development, Institutional Constraints and Adaptation Strategies, Personal and Professional Capacity Building, and Affective Experiences. Findings indicated that students pursued entrepreneurship for financial independence and skill development while facing challenges in balancing academic and business demands. Support from family and peers proved crucial in sustaining entrepreneurial engagement. Participants demonstrated ethical awareness through customer-based pricing strategies that considered student budgets while maintaining quality standards. Potential skill development and financial gain shaped perceived desirability, while market accessibility and parental support influenced perceived feasibility. The study concludes that student entrepreneurship brings rewards and pressures, requiring balance between academic and business roles. These findings fill a gap in literature on junior high school entrepreneurs in STEM contexts, with implications for educational policy reform and future research.

Keywords: *student entrepreneurship, lived experiences, junior high school, entrepreneurial motivation, qualitative research*

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CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is the skill involved in starting new businesses, especially regarding finding new opportunities (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025). In 2022, a total of 932,097 new business name registrations were recorded in the Philippines, showing the prevalence of entrepreneurship in the modern day world (Department of Trade and Industry, 2022). As such, it is a widely regarded means of generating income among the youth, and a way to realize financial independence and responsibility.

Student entrepreneurs are those who conduct profitable entrepreneurial activities while attending formal classes (Manipon, 2025). They are responsible for a significant number of business startups and develop practical business skills that can be utilized beyond the classroom (Chahinez & Meriem, 2023; Longva, 2021). These students demonstrate resourcefulness and diligence, usually by looking for ways to meet the demands or orders of classmates (Pratiwi & Zahroh, 2023). In contrast to conventional part-time jobs, which restrict the student's schedule, self-managed businesses allow for flexibility and involvement in the financial decision-making process (Balmaceda & Ona, 2023). This flexibility allows them to be able to comply with school-related tasks while upholding their businesses.

Entrepreneurship can influence students' lifestyles and vice versa while also contributing to the development and honing of other skills, such as critical thinking,

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adaptability, leadership qualities, and communication abilities. In addition to encouraging financial independence, understanding the motivations involved could provide insights on emerging trends and opportunities for workers. Nevertheless, student entrepreneurs often encounter challenges throughout their entrepreneurship that hinder their progress and success, such as lack of financial resources and funding, time commitment, and academic responsibilities (Hanafi et al., 2024). Exploring these challenges could help in reducing the burdens and stresses that are imposed on students.

Entrepreneurial intentions are shaped by a network of decision-making processes pushed or pulled by different factors. Etrata and Raborar (2022) stated that entrepreneurial intent is influenced not only by individual competencies—such as entrepreneurial attitude, skills, and knowledge—but most importantly by social valuation, namely the environment and the people surrounding the entrepreneur. According to Xanthopoulou and Sahinidis (2024), students' entrepreneurial intentions are shaped by their social environment, including family, peers, and educators, as social valuation can either encourage or discourage students from pursuing entrepreneurial ventures. Therefore, with the promotion of a supportive culture of entrepreneurship, educational institutions can empower students to turn their ideas into viable businesses. Understanding the factors that influence entrepreneurial intent can help educators and policymakers develop targeted interventions to support student entrepreneurs to have mentorship programs and access to resources.

Several studies have investigated the underlying reasons and implications

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resulting from the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs from different student populations. However, a clear research gap exists as most of the studies primarily focused on senior high school and college graduates, which limits the generalizability of the findings of the research undertaken to younger student populations, such as the junior high school department. Early adolescence is a critical developmental stage due to identity formation, cognitive maturation, and increasing autonomy (UCLA Center for the Developing Adolescent, 2025). However, this population gap restricts the understanding of how entrepreneurial intentions and behaviors emerge in younger students who have not received formal entrepreneurship education. Thus, to increase the investigation into entrepreneurship in school, research can be done extending to junior high school students.

Furthermore, methodological gaps surfaced among research studies. Similar studies to Gaddi et al. (2024) examined the factors influencing the entrepreneurial intention of Senior High School students using quantitative measures, unable to take into account other qualitative measures that focus on the students' personal experiences, deep-rooted motivations, socio-emotional influences, and barriers that explain their commitment to entrepreneurship (Tian et al., 2022). The studies focused on exploring what was the intention itself, rather than how those intentions, paired with certain circumstances, affected the students' decisions to perform entrepreneurial action. This emphasizes the need for a deeper exploration of how students' entrepreneurial experiences are affected by their intentions and environment.

To establish a foundational understanding of student entrepreneurship within

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SRSTHS, the researchers conducted a preliminary survey prior to the main study. The survey, which collected responses from a total of 70 students across various grade levels and sections, aimed to probe the prevalence and visibility of student entrepreneurial activity within the school community. Respondents spanned from Grade 7 through Grade 11, representing a cross-section of the student population, and all participants formally consented to the processing of their data for research purposes.

The survey, located in Appendix B, revealed that 11 out of 70 respondents (approximately 15.7%) identified themselves as student entrepreneurs. Of these 11 student entrepreneurs, 8 reported selling their products within school grounds, while 3 indicated that their business activities take place outside of the school campus. The nature and scale of their ventures varied considerably: some sold food items such as *yema*, candy, *onigiri*, cookies, and beverages, while others offered non-food products and services such as perfumes and commissions. Monthly sales volumes ranged widely, from a few items or commissions per month to several hundred or even thousands of units at peak periods, reflecting the diverse scales at which student entrepreneurs operate.

Additionally, when non-entrepreneur respondents were asked whether they were aware of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS, 37 out of 70 (approximately 52.9%) confirmed that they personally knew at least one student entrepreneur, with many citing knowledge of two to five individuals engaged in such activities. This finding underscores that student entrepreneurship, while practiced by a minority, is nonetheless a visible and recognized phenomenon within the school. These preliminary results provided the

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researchers with sufficient basis to affirm the existence of a student entrepreneur population in SRSTHS and justified the need for a more in-depth qualitative inquiry into the lived experiences of these student entrepreneurs.

This study aimed to address these gaps by using a qualitative method to examine the underlying motivations behind SRSTHS students who engage in entrepreneurship. By employing interviews, the study explored how different factors such as perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, social influences, and existing barriers influence the students' entrepreneurial behaviors. The study aimed to find and understand the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School (SRSTHS).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on established theoretical perspectives (Inoubli, 2024) which explain the relationships between the variables under investigation. Shapero and Sokol's Entrepreneurial Event Model grounds this study, explaining that entrepreneurial action as the product of interacting perceptual and situational factors. The model considers that entrepreneurship occurs when an individual perceives the activity as desirable and feasible, and possesses an inclination to act on opportunities. In the context of student entrepreneurship, perceived desirability reflects the extent to which students view entrepreneurial activity as attractive and socially supported within their academic and social environment. Perceived feasibility refers to students' beliefs regarding their

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capability to initiate and manage entrepreneurial activities, shaped by their skills, resources, and access to institutional support. These perceptions are often activated by displacement events, such as financial needs or the recognition of unmet demands within the school setting, which disrupt routine paths and motivate entrepreneurial behavior (Shapero & Sokol, 1982).

Figure 1

Shapero and Sokol's Entrepreneurial Event Model

Further foundation is provided by the Theory of Planned Behavior, which explains that behavior is a function of intention shaped by cognitive and social factors.

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According to the theory, intention to perform a behavior is influenced by attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Attitude toward the behavior reflects students' evaluations of entrepreneurship as beneficial or worthwhile. Subjective norms refer to perceived social pressure from peers, family members, and educators regarding engagement in entrepreneurial activities. Considering available skills and resources, perceived behavioral control represents students' beliefs about their capacity to successfully initiate and sustain entrepreneurial endeavors. These components together shape students' entrepreneurial intentions, which immediately precedes entrepreneurial behavior (Ajzen, 1991).

Figure 2

Model of Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior

In addition to the aforementioned saxa, this study also considers Rotter's concept of Locus of Control. Rotter (1966) distinguishes between individuals who attribute

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outcomes to their own actions (internal locus) and those who attribute outcomes to external factors such as luck, fate, or powerful others (external locus). Within the context of student entrepreneurship, students with an internal locus of control are more likely to take initiative and persist in entrepreneurial activities because they perceive their efforts as directly influencing success. Conversely, students with an external locus of control may hesitate to engage in entrepreneurial ventures or abandon them quickly. These types of people often attribute setbacks to circumstances beyond their control. Understanding students with different loci of control provides insight into how their perceptions of personal agency interact with entrepreneurial intentions and behavior, thus complementing frameworks such as the Entrepreneurial Event Model and the Theory of Planned Behavior.

Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual framework is anchored on Pham et al. (2023), centered on the lived experiences of students who are entrepreneurs at Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School. This allows for the assessment of the factors that influenced their entrepreneurial engagement, including social and push-and-pull business factors. Subsequently, the manner in which these lived experiences have impacted the student entrepreneurs' lifestyle, educational performance, and job prospects, as well as the implications of the results on the root cause of the increasing prevalence of student entrepreneurship.

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Figure 3

Conceptual framework

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to assess the lived experiences of SRSTHS student entrepreneurs. The findings of this study provide insights into the different factors that may affect or be affected by the students' participation in entrepreneurial activities. Specifically, this study a to answer the following sub-problems:

Central question:

1. What are the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?

Corollary questions:

1. What are the different motivations of SRSTHS students for pursuing student entrepreneurship?
2. What are the different challenges faced by student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?
3. How do perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and social influences shape entrepreneurial intention among SRSTHS students?

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4. What are the ethical considerations taken into account by the student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?

Significance of the Study

The results of this study aim to benefit **students** by providing insights on the motivations, challenges, and overall lived experiences of student entrepreneurs, enabling them to recognize the personal, socio-emotional, and academic factors that influence decisions and behaviors associated with entrepreneurship. For **parents and guardians**, this study can help provide an understanding of their children's motivations, challenges, and skills gained through entrepreneurship, allowing for better guidance and support. Lastly, this study serves as a possible reference for **future researchers**. Student researchers could use the researchers' findings to formulate methodologies and explore alternative perspectives and interpretations regarding the lived experience of student entrepreneurs.

Scope and Delimitation

This study aims to assess SRSTHS student entrepreneurs' experiences, exploring the complexities of managing a business while navigating academic responsibilities. The scope of this study includes SRSTHS students who fit the study's criteria of "student entrepreneurs."

The study will take place over the second semester, utilizing interviews to gain

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qualitative data regarding the profile and experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS.

This study will only involve students enrolled in SRSTHS. It will not assess student businesses that are incentivized by the school, such as subject projects or club activities. Likewise, this study will not consider customer feedback, whether it be in the form of satisfaction with products sold or the broader assessment of the business' services.

The study will only look into specific aspects of the students personal backgrounds such as their grade levels and economic backgrounds. With this, the research can focus on what student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS have in common, like the challenges that they face, what drives them to run a business, and how they tackle problems they encounter, instead of comparing the social demographic differences between the students.

Definition of Terms

For a better understanding of this study, the following terms are defined in the context of this research.

Entrepreneurship. According to Cambridge Dictionary (2025), it is the skill in starting new businesses, especially when this involves seeing new opportunities. In this study, entrepreneurship refers to the act of selling products or services to customers.

Student Entrepreneur. Those who conduct profitable entrepreneurial activities while attending formal classes (Manipon, 2025). In the context of this study, student

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entrepreneurs are defined as students enrolled in SRSTHS who have sold products or services to customers in or outside the school for a minimum of six months. These businesses are not incentivized by the school, which would mean they are not affiliated with school-required projects, subject activities, or school organizations. The entrepreneurial activity must be of the student's own volition.

Lived Experiences. A self-given situational awareness based on immediate knowledge and experience of reality (Samra, 2025). Specifically, this study seeks to find the lived experience of SRSTHS student entrepreneurs regarding their entrepreneurial intentions, motivations, challenges, perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and ethical considerations.

Motivations. According to Cambridge Dictionary (2025), it is the need or reason for doing something. In this study, the motivations pertained to are the motives of student entrepreneurs in pursuing entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurial Intention. It is the conviction of the person to perform entrepreneurial actions at some point in the future (Relente & Capistrano, 2024). In this study, it refers to the intent of student entrepreneurs to pursue entrepreneurial jobs in future ventures.

Perceived Desirability. It is the appraised cognitive value or attraction of an entrepreneurial opportunity (Khuyen et al., 2023). In this study, it refers to student entrepreneurs' beliefs regarding how interesting entrepreneurial activities are.

Perceived Feasibility. It is the appraised viability and difficulty in pursuing an entrepreneurial opportunity (Khuyen et al., 2023). In this study, it refers to student

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entrepreneurs' beliefs regarding their capability to initiate and manage entrepreneurial activities, shaped by their skills, resources, and access to institutional support.

Challenges. According to Cambridge Dictionary (2025), it is something that needs great effort, whether physical or mental, to be overcome. In this study, it refers to the different obstacles that student entrepreneurs experience.

Ethical Considerations. According to Cambridge Dictionary (2025), these are the thoughts considered in line with beliefs about what is morally correct. In this study, these refer to the moral factors that affect the actions and considerations of student entrepreneurs.

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CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter contains relevant literature and studies from local and foreign sources. It contains information regarding concepts, theories, and variables related to the study, organized by theme. This chapter aims to provide the readers with a comprehensive understanding of the study's subject.

Student Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is generally conceptualized as the creation of value in a way that positively contributes to society. It is the identification of business-related opportunities via existing, new, or a recombination of resources in an innovative manner (Ratten, 2023). Schimperna et al. (2021) defined entrepreneurship as a process of being creative, inventive, and adventurous through the development of ideas using available resources. If a market or demand is not present in an area, that would create an opportunity for an entrepreneur to establish one. Thus, entrepreneurs serve as both creators and innovators of products (Caliat, 2024).

Within this entrepreneurial framework, students constitute an important unit of society, as they are widely regarded as the ones to shape the future and direction of a nation. Given that entrepreneurship is a driving factor of the national economy, student participation stimulates demand and accelerates economic activity (Ayob, 2021). In the past, student entrepreneurship was a term used exclusively for students enrolled in entrepreneurship courses or programs. However, researchers argued for a broader

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definition, instead describing student entrepreneurs as students who conduct profitable and revenue-generating entrepreneurial activities within school premises while simultaneously attending formal classes (Cucino et al., 2022; Manipon, 2025). Essentially, student entrepreneurs are those that take advantage of their school environment to strategically employ their business. These students identify opportunities and meet the needs, requests, or orders of their classmates (Pratiwi & Zahroh, 2023).

According to Longva (2021), student entrepreneurs make up a substantial portion of business startups. Some of the world's biggest enterprises were founded when the owners were still students, with a notable example being Facebook which was founded when Mark Zuckerberg was still an undergraduate student at Harvard University (Kabonga & Zvokuomba, 2021). This aligns with the findings showing that enterprises founded by students create and transfer new knowledge to the market while also generating employment. This exposure to entrepreneurship during their studies fosters an entrepreneurial mindset and equips students with skills that provide flexibility when choosing future careers (Passavanti et al., 2023).

Entrepreneurial Competencies

Entrepreneurial Competencies are the foundations for effective business management and performance, merging the abilities, personality, and mindset of an individual in the context of entrepreneurship. As stated in the study of Koçyiğit et al. (2024), competencies in entrepreneurship provide a standard framework to adhere to,

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enabling entrepreneurs to implement appropriate strategies to attain higher performance and a higher success rate. Thereby, accentuating the role of competencies in the field of business is crucial, as it constantly evolves in response to the changing demands and emerging trends of the contemporary setting to remain relevant, effective, and competitive. In line with this perspective, entrepreneurial competence is categorized into eight: opportunity, relationship, conceptual, organising, strategic, commitment, learning, and personal strength (García-Cabrera et al., 2023).

Opportunity Recognition. An entrepreneur seeks opportunities in every situation, which leads to the initial process of starting a business through concept generation and concept evaluation (Baggen, 2017, as cited in Hartono & Ardini, 2022). It begins with acknowledging an idea's potential to become large, relevant, and profitable by thinking creatively, then assessing its potential impact on the market, addressing any areas for improvement, and eventually coming up with an effective strategy for execution.

Relationship Competency. Expanding and extending partnerships is essential for a business to gain recognition from a wider audience. This involves communication and social skills that encourage audience engagement and emphasize and understand the demands and preferences of the target market. Furthermore, within entrepreneurship, there is a business ecosystem recognized in the study of Baumann & Leerhoff (2022) that aligns with relationship-based competency. It is a type of ecosystem consisting of various individuals with the need to interact, such as suppliers, customers, distributors, government, products, and competitors, to establish an understanding of

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interconnectedness that would lead to continual input for the entrepreneur's improvement and their ability to adapt to customer needs while both are being sustainable and constructive.

Conceptual Competency. As per Blignaut and Botha (2024), entrepreneurs are exposed to a variety of complex situations that allow them to develop a holistic perspective for the purpose of pinpointing the areas that must undergo strategic planning as well as action in order to improve and remain competitive in the 21st century industry. Thus, an individual in the entrepreneurial field possesses distinct organizational and mapping skills to arrange ideas and thoughts and arrive at a clear conclusion and direction.

Strategic Competency. Pursuant to studies conducted by Iskandar et al. (2022), Soomro et al. (2024), and Kumar et al. (2025), strategic competencies significantly improve a social enterprise's performance through the combination of adequate preparation, management, and utilization in finance, innovation, and technology. These findings render strategic competencies a significant skill that, when observed and practiced, has beneficial implications. The field of entrepreneurship is competitive and offers an extensive range of products that are derived from the current in-demand recognized by entrepreneurs. However, since the goal of entrepreneurs is to meet the needs of society, it is inevitable that other entrepreneurs end up coming across a similar idea. As a result, strategies for production, exhibition, and distribution are necessary to

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gain an advantage over competitors and ensure that one's product or service stays relevant over time while adapting to changing trends and unforeseen circumstances.

Commitment Competency. Being able to operate as an entrepreneur in conjunction with one's role while being passionate motivates one to strive for improved and greater goals. Drawing on the studies of Josimovska et al. (2025) and Boussema (2023), an entrepreneur's strong emotional commitment encourages them to be more creative and innovative while being hands-on in their role because they are emotionally invested in it. However, they also have a tendency to neglect real market demand because they firmly believe that their idea is inherent and can still be recognized in the market, overshadowing the need for external feedback, timely action, and dismissing competitors' prospective tactics with their product decreasing its competitive advantage.

Learning Competency. Given that it refers to what an individual can do and offer in the community instead of merely what they know about the process of producing products and providing services, learning competency is a distinctive skill that makes them stand out on the entrepreneurial course they have taken, turning their learned or innate skill into their competitive advantage and focus of market or service. As shown by McCrea & Mirchandani (2025) and Kim et al. (2025), experiential learning in line with business learning competencies has a positive effect on sustained skill and ability development. Since experiential learning exposes entrepreneurs to scenarios requiring an aptitude for critical thinking and the capacity to lead others and themselves toward a

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single, clear objective while maintaining constant communication, they are able to integrate and adapt in various kinds of situations.

Personal Strength Competency. It is the collection of skills and knowledge that people either naturally possess or acquire, which allows them to better perceive and prosper in the entrepreneurial environment. In this line of work, their strongest qualities are combined with other existing micro and macro attributes, which help them not only complement and develop their intrinsic skills but also increase their chances of surviving outside of the corporate world. The results of the studies by López-Fernández & Romero-Fernández (2025) and Savita et al. (2025) demonstrated that personal strength serves as a foundation for beginning and sustaining one's business, whilst also being able to manage duties and commitments in addition to remaining conscious of one's own needs and well-being. Personal strength of individuals increases competency, likelihood of success, and staying put over time, considering they are well-equipped with the right resources.

Moreover, these competencies correlate with the psychological component of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (ESE), which is the conviction that one can launch and successfully manage a business (Ye & Kang, 2025). Individuals who acquire skills and knowledge in entrepreneurship are more likely to use entrepreneurial competencies as a benchmark for their level of confidence when running a business (Sari & Sari, 2022). Should these competences are put together and utilized strategically, an entrepreneur

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becomes more equipped to navigate the field with confidence in their own abilities, embody them, and connect them with their peers.

Foundations of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurial intention refers to a person's willingness and desire to start a business in the future (Bird, 1988; Krueger & Carsrud, 1993, as cited in Liñeiro et al., 2024). It shows how seriously an individual thinks about becoming an entrepreneur and planning to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Starting a business does not happen suddenly but begins with a clear intention. Therefore, entrepreneurial intention is considered an important factor in understanding why some individuals choose to pursue entrepreneurship while others do not.

Personality factors have an important role in influencing the students' entrepreneurial intention because personality aspects will directly influence students' confidence to embark on the entrepreneurial venture. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy, perceived by the student as the capability to effectively execute the task of starting a business, has discovered its importance to significantly influence the intention to have an entrepreneurial career. A student with high self-efficacy will have the confidence to overcome obstacles to take the initiative to start a business because they feel they have the ability to handle the challenges (Li et al., 2023). Risk-taking propensity also affects the intention because students who have no problem with risk are more likely to consider the inception of a business as one of the viable career alternatives for them (Martins et al.,

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2023). Other variables such as need for achievement and motivation will also have an important effect because students who act to achieve success will have the tendency to involve themselves in the business process (Hidayah & Rodhiah, 2024). Moreover, the trait of creativity will enable the student to develop new ideas to identify entrepreneurial opportunities that will boost the students' confidence to start the business (Ulfah & Syahrudin, 2024).

Entrepreneurial knowledge is gained and accumulated through formal education, business interaction, and practical business records, supplying individuals the opportunities to learn and develop practical skills, critical thinking, and problem solving abilities tantamount to entrepreneurial success (Hussain et al., 2021). This is especially crucial because of the high failure rates that are common in developing nations, where business owners must overcome obstacles and use their entrepreneurial expertise to leverage resources for better performance outputs (Soomro et al., 2024).

According to a study by Zeng et al. (2023), art and design students at higher technical colleges benefit greatly from entrepreneurship expertise. Understanding business ideas, market possibilities, risk management, and innovative techniques is essential for starting and maintaining entrepreneurial activities, based on the study, which included semi-structured interviews with students at various levels of entrepreneurial participation. Gaining entrepreneurial knowledge through formal education, contests, and hands-on training improves critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills, laying the groundwork for entrepreneurial preparedness.

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Furthermore, the Theory of Planned Behavior and Social Cognitive Career Theory view entrepreneurial knowledge as a cognitive resource that functions indirectly through individual and self-efficacy. Meta-analytic findings based on their study concludes that entrepreneurial knowledge influences how people evaluate the feasibility and desirability of entrepreneurship rather than acting as a standalone driver of entrepreneurial intention. Entrepreneurial knowledge, when incorporated into favorable social and educational settings, enhances entrepreneurial readiness by facilitating decision-making, lowering perceived uncertainty, and boosting confidence (Liao et al., 2022).

Policy Foundations for Youth Entrepreneurship in the Philippines

The Philippines formally recognizes entrepreneurship as a critical strategy for youth development and economic growth. Republic Act No. 10679 institutionalizes this by mandating the integration of entrepreneurship and financial literacy across all levels of the educational system, from elementary to tertiary education (Youth Entrepreneurship Act, 2014). Its primary goal is to shift the youth mindset from being job seekers to job creators, thereby addressing unemployment through education. This law led to tangible structural changes, most notably the establishment of the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand in the Senior High School curriculum. This policy direction is reinforced by the Philippine Development Plan (PDP) 2023–2028, which emphasizes building an innovation ecosystem. The plan specifically advocates for the digital

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transformation of MSMEs and calls for the establishment of Technology Business Incubators (TBIs) within academic institutions to help translate student ideas into market-ready products (Navo, 2024).

The implementation of entrepreneurship education under this policy framework has been a subject of local research. A study by Maroma (2024) found that Grade 10 students in Bulacan exhibited only a moderate level of awareness of entrepreneurship opportunities. Furthermore, Castro et al. (2023) found no significant relationship between academic performance and entrepreneurial attitude among Grade 12 ABM students, which suggests that academic success does not solely drive entrepreneurial mindset. Therefore, there is a clear gap between intent and implementation in youth entrepreneurship programs. This underscores the complexity of furthering entrepreneurship, which may depend more on experiential learning and attitude formation than conventional academic achievement.

Despite these gaps, the intent of the curriculum is clear: to equip students with practical competencies. As outlined in the Youth Entrepreneurship Act (2014), mandated skills include market research, business planning, and social entrepreneurship. Research from other contexts supports this experiential approach; Lyu et al. (2023) concluded that practical-focused pedagogy contributes more significantly to the entrepreneurial process than theoretical-focused methods. Similarly, T. T. Nguyen et al. (2021) highlighted the significant impact of entrepreneurship extracurricular activities and inspiration on entrepreneurial intention, affirming the importance of learning beyond the classroom.

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Existing literature provides a strong foundation on entrepreneurial intention through quantitative surveys and outlines the macro-level policy environment. However, a significant gap remains in qualitative, in-depth explorations of the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs within the unique context of Philippine senior high schools, especially specialized science and technology institutions. Most studies focus on university students or broad senior high school populations (Hutasuhut & Adita, 2022; Schimperna et al., 2021). There is a lack of deep, contextual understanding of the daily realities, challenges, motivations, and coping strategies of students who balance the demands of a rigorous science and technology curriculum with the pressures of running a business.

Theories on Entrepreneurial Behavior

Julian B. Rotter's (1966) social learning theory (as cited in Hamzah & Othman, 2023) introduces Locus of Control as a core personality construct explaining an individual's generalized expectancy regarding outcome causality. It establishes a continuum:

Internal Locus of Control. The belief that outcomes are determined by one's own actions, efforts, and personal agency.

External Locus of Control. The belief that outcomes are controlled by external forces such as luck, fate, or powerful others.

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This construct is crucial for entrepreneurship, as individuals with an internal locus are more likely to proactively seek opportunities, persist through challenges, and believe they can "create" their future through venture creation. It provides the foundational lens for understanding the personal agency and resilience exhibited by student entrepreneurs at SRSTHS.

While Locus of Control explains a key personal driver, Inoubli's (2024) theoretical reviews provides a vital integrative structure. Inoubli synthesizes classic models like the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the Entrepreneurial Event Model (Shapero & Sokol, 1982) with modern influences, arguing that entrepreneurial intention is a multi-dimensional construct.

Individual Personality Traits. Such as need for achievement, risk-taking propensity, and crucially, internal locus of control, which aligns with the concept of "perceived feasibility."

Environmental and Digital Factors. Including university (or school) support systems, the economic climate, and the rise of digital entrepreneurship platforms and opportunities.

Role of Education. Inoubli (2024) concludes that education is paramount in instilling the "perceived feasibility" of entrepreneurship among students, thereby directly linking institutional and pedagogical support to individual intention.

The Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM) developed by Shapero and Sokol is a foundational model that aims to properly define the concept of an entrepreneurial event.

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It classifies factors that affect entrepreneurial intention into three main groups: negative displacements, intermediate situations, and positive displacements. Negative displacements are factors that dissuade individuals from pursuing entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, intermediate situations are those that trigger change in an individual's inclination toward entrepreneurship. In contrast, positive displacements are factors that motivate individuals to pursue entrepreneurship (Inoubli, 2024). Additionally, the EEM is based on the premise that an individual's choice to become an entrepreneur is anchored on three main factors: perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and propensity to act. However, perceived desirability and perceived feasibility are the primary focus of most research involving the EEM (Nitu-Antoine et al., 2023).

Perceived desirability is a person's view on the attractiveness of an idea, while perceived feasibility refers to a person's belief in their ability to create their own business (Duong et al., 2025). In a study conducted by Ambad (2022), these two components were found to affect entrepreneurial intention. However, many factors can also affect perceived desirability and feasibility. In a study conducted by Jabid et al. (2023), both perceived desirability and feasibility were found to be mediated by entrepreneurial education. Moreover, Abdelkarim (2021) found that students support the introduction of entrepreneurial education to further increase entrepreneurial desirability. Pineda et al. (2023) also linked perceived desirability to a university context, highlighting the role of education in stimulating entrepreneurial interest.

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In the modern age, technology is an integral part of daily life. Thus, several studies have investigated the role of different technologies in enhancing the basis of the EEM. Pham et al. (2023) found that the technological innovativeness of students mediated their entrepreneurial intentions and motivations. Furthermore, studies have shown that the incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) like ChatGPT positively impacts perceived desirability and feasibility (Duong et al., 2025; T. Nguyen et al., 2025). These findings emphasize the role of newfound technology in encouraging entrepreneurship based on the EEM.

Shapero and Sokol also highlighted the existence of triggering events in the EEM. Triggering events refer to occurrences that cause an individual to change their behavior and attitude towards entrepreneurship. However, a study conducted by Ruiz-Rosa et al. (2021) found that graduates in the start-up process tend to overestimate the importance of triggering events, highlighting that real-life experience is more crucial in the development of entrepreneurial intention. Pham et al. (2023) also found that along with entrepreneurial education, prior experiences serve as the main driving force behind students' entrepreneurial intentions. Thus, exploring the lived experiences of entrepreneurs is crucial in order to effectively investigate entrepreneurial intentions. With the context provided by the findings of these studies, the EEM can be used as a reliable basis for the framework of this research.

Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is a model that explains behavior as a result of intention shaped by several factors. These factors include an individual's

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attitude, subjective norms, and their perceptions of behavioral control (Hagger et al., 2022). The model is utilized in studies that aim to investigate the attitudes and intentions behind human behavior. Pillai et al. (2022) utilized the TPB to investigate the purchase intentions and attitudes of online food delivery service consumers. Meanwhile, Lee et al. (2023) integrated the TPB with the Value-Belief-Norm Theory to aid in analyzing the intentions behind the use of electric vehicles.

In the context of entrepreneurship, the TPB has been used to analyze the entrepreneurial intentions and behaviors of individuals. A study conducted by Lihua (2022) adopted the TPB as the theoretical framework for discovering the entrepreneurial intentions of college students. Meanwhile, Sampene et al. (2023) examined the entrepreneurial intentions of university students from Ghana through the lens of the TPB. Similarly, Barrios et al. (2021) used the TPB as a basis for exploring the entrepreneurial intentions of Colombian university students. These studies show the crucial role of TPB as a framework for investigating the factors that may affect the intentions and behaviors of students regarding entrepreneurship.

Additionally, it is demonstrated that the theory of planned behavior has been adopted by all generations and populations. Relente & Capistrano's (2025) study on youth entrepreneurship uses confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling to demonstrate how innovation self-efficacy, attitude toward entrepreneurship, and perceived behavioral control can significantly influence an individual's entrepreneurial intention, while a subjective norm was found to have no direct impact. On the other hand,

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Lloren-Alcantara & Capistrano's (2025) study used TPB to investigate consumers' purchase intentions toward social enterprises in the Philippines. The results revealed that attitudes toward social enterprises showed significant results, subjective norms showed mixed and contrarian results, and perceived behavioral control showed insignificant results.

Meanwhile, in the study of Passaro et al. (2025), TPB was expanded to examine small enterprises' intentions to invest in energy transition strategies. The results showed that intention precedes actual conduct. Expectations related to the economy and finances also have a big impact on intention. It was substantiated in the study by Boucif et al. (2025) that while subjective norms indirectly affect intention through attitude, attitude and perceived behavioral control strongly predict entrepreneurial intention. Additionally, it was discovered that perceived behavioral control was improved by relational and familial support. Subsequently, Murad et al. (2025) found that academic entrepreneurial intention is strongly influenced by entrepreneurial networks, with attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control serving as mediators.

Synthesis

The reviewed literature collectively constructs a multidimensional understanding of student entrepreneurship, progressing from broad conceptual foundations to the specific psychological and institutional factors at play. It establishes entrepreneurship as a critical engine for economic development and personal growth, with students emerging as

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a vital cohort within this ecosystem (Ayob, 2021). The definitions have exposed the practical and opportunistic nature of ventures undertaken within the school environment: from formal academic pursuits to include any profit-generating activity managed alongside formal studies (Pratiwi & Zahroh, 2023).

A strong emphasis is placed on the competencies required for entrepreneurial success, framing them as a blend of skills, mindset, and strategic action. These competencies, ranging from opportunity recognition and strategic planning to relationship management and personal resilience, provide a framework for assessing the capabilities student entrepreneurs develop through lived experience (Koçyiğit et al., 2024). This ties directly into the psychological drivers of entrepreneurial intention, where personality traits like self-efficacy, risk tolerance, and creativity are shown to be significant predictors of the desire to start a business (Li et al., 2023; Martins et al., 2023; Ulfah & Syahrudin, 2024).

The Philippine context adds a critical institutional layer to this discussion. National policies explicitly aim to cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset from an early age, integrating it into the education system through specific tracks and support mechanisms (Youth Entrepreneurship Act, 2014). However, studies suggest a potential gap between this policy intent and on-the-ground awareness among students, indicating that structural support alone may not suffice without affecting personal attitudes and perceived feasibility (Hutasuhut & Adita, 2022; Schimperna et al., 2021).

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This is where the theoretical models converge to offer a powerful lens. The Entrepreneurial Event Model and the Theory of Planned Behavior provide complementary frameworks for understanding how intentions are formed (Hagger et al., 2022; Inoubli, 2024). They identify key levers: the perceived desirability shaped by social and cultural norms, the perceived feasibility influenced by resources and self-belief, and the propensity to act triggered by personal or environmental circumstances. The concept of Locus of Control further deepens this analysis by explaining the underlying belief systems that determine whether students attribute outcomes to their own efforts or to external forces, fundamentally shaping their initiative and perseverance (Rotter, 1966, as cited in Hamzah & Othman, 2023).

Having taken note of all of this, there is undoubtedly still a significant research gap in the qualitative, lived experiences especially in junior high school and specialized high school students. Most research conducted on student entrepreneurship centers around university and senior high school students, and focuses more on the quantitative aspect and intention rather than lived experiences. There is limited deep understanding of how student entrepreneurs, particularly within specialized environments like a Science high school, navigate the daily interplay between their academic responsibilities, their developing competencies, their internal psychological drivers, and the external institutional environment. This study aims to bridge these gaps by exploring the unified narrative of the lived experience, thus providing a holistic view of what it means to be a student entrepreneur at SRSTHS.

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CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the research design and methodology to be used for the study. These procedures were determined after careful consideration of the studies objectives and the information obtained from related literature.

Research Design

A phenomenological study is a qualitative research design that uses people's experiences to explain the nature of a phenomenon (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). The study used this approach to determine the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS. In this way, the study was able to find how the motivations, challenges, perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, social influences and ethical considerations were taken into account by student entrepreneurs. Conducting the study with a phenomenological approach helped the researchers further understand the experiences of participants.

Sources of Data

Data collection was done through both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained from face-to-face, semi-structured interviews with selected SRSTHS student entrepreneurs, following approaches that aligned with numerous phenomenological studies of student entrepreneurship. Additional literature and

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published materials, such as articles, journals, books, and government records, will be used as secondary sources for cross-examination and data interpretation.

Participants of the Study

The researchers selected five (5) SRTHS student entrepreneurs as participants of the study. Nielsen and Launder (1993), as cited by Budiu (2021), validated this number of participants by developing a mathematical model demonstrating that a qualitative test with 5 individuals can discover 85% of the problems in an interface. In addition, Nielsen recommends testing with 5 participants first and identifying 85% of their problems before testing with another 5 participants, and so on.

A purposive sampling technique was used to select the participants of the study based on the following criteria: 1) student entrepreneurs enrolled in SRSTHS for the school year 2025-2026, 2) currently engaged in entrepreneurial activities that are not incentivized by the school, and lastly 3) with at least 6 months of experience in entrepreneurship.

Instrumentation

To investigate the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs at SRSTHS, the researchers first conducted a pilot survey using Google Forms, the results of which can be seen in Appendix B. The instrument was disseminated among SRSTHS students to screen for eligible participants of the study.

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A semi-structured interview served as the main instrument for data collection. According to George (2023), this instrument is best used when the research questions are exploratory in nature. It contained open-ended questions designed in accordance with the principles of phenomenological research, with an emphasis on the experiences of the participants as student entrepreneurs. The interviews were audio recorded upon the participants' consent and field notes were taken to document nonverbal cues and contextual observations.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study explored the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs from students at SRSTHS and adopted a phenomenological approach within qualitative research. The investigation followed systematic procedures to ensure rigor, independence, and ethical integrity throughout the research process.

First, approval from the administration of SRSTHS and other pertinent authorities was formally requested and obtained to conduct the study onsite. This step was undertaken to ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). Adherence to this law was essential to safeguard the respondents' fundamental right to privacy, protecting their name and personal information, and preventing any data gathered throughout the study approach from being misused.

Upon approval, participants were selected using non-random purposive sampling based on the established criteria for student entrepreneurs, in which the participants of the

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study consisted of student entrepreneurs who are currently enrolled in SRSTHS who are independently operating a business that is not affiliated with school-required projects, subject activities, or school organizations. As per Tajik et al. (2024), there were specific units designed to choose participants relevant to the research questions. Eligible participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their rights as participants. Informed consent was obtained prior to the collection of data. For participants who are minors, parental consent was also secured.

To gather information about possible participants who meet the criteria of student entrepreneurs, a pre-survey was conducted before the interview process began. The pre-survey was only used for screening, such as verifying the respondents' grade level, enrollment status, and participation in independent business endeavors. By conducting this step, the researchers were able to assess participant eligibility and make sure that the study only includes eligible student entrepreneurs.

Based on the pre-survey results, five (5) qualified SRSTHS students were selected for the interview stage to adequately represent the population of student entrepreneurs. Then, for the purpose of acquiring comprehensive information about the students' experiences as entrepreneurs, data was collected through individual semi-structured interviews that align with numerous phenomenological studies of student entrepreneurship. In addition, to protect participants' privacy and avoid interfering with their academic obligations, the interviews took place at a time and place that are mutually agreed upon. In assuring proper documentation of responses, the interviews were audio

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recorded with the participants' consent. During the interviews, field notes were taken to document relevant observations.

After the interviews, the audio recordings were transcribed verbatim. To maintain confidentiality, pseudonyms will be assigned to each participant, and any identifying information was removed from the transcripts. All collected data were securely stored and used solely for this research. The transcribed data was then prepared for analysis to identify common themes related to the experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers followed the formal stages of communication to adhere to ethical considerations. A consent form was provided to the participants to inform them of how their information will be used in the study. Additionally, it ensured the anonymity of the participants and outlined their right to withdraw from the study at any time. The participant, their legal guardian, and the researchers provided their signatures to signify informed consent. Finally, audio recordings and verbatim transcriptions of the interview were obtained with the participant's agreement.

Treatment and Analysis of Data

This section explains how the collected data will be analyzed and prepared for interpretation. To understand the underlying implications of the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs, it is necessary to conduct a thorough analysis of the themes,

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emerging patterns, and experiences. The qualitative nature of the study is best complemented by thematic analysis to bring out themes emerging from the students' experience.

Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is the process of data examination wherein the researchers are actively involved in constructing meaning from the emerging patterns in the collective experiences (Braun & Clarke, 2021). From the input of the respondents, the researchers aim to build a network of themes that tell a story on how motivations, challenges, intention, and social experiences contribute to the overall lived experience of the student entrepreneur. This is possible using a deductive analysis technique to understand specific underlying processes emerging from general statements. To align with established frameworks, this study employed a systematic six-phase process.

Phase 1. After collection, the first step is to understand and familiarize oneself with the data (Braun & Clarke, 2021). This stage is crucial to be able to conduct a general overview of the data. This involves reading, summarizing, and re-reading the interview transcripts in order to produce meaningful and coherent “codes” to be identified, and patterns to emerge. The researcher actively immerses themselves in the data to identify general patterns on motivations, challenges, intention, and experiences and to rid the future of any outlying information that might detract from the overall validity.

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Phase 2. Identification of codes is the next step, in which the transcripts are broken down into smaller units, such as phrases or sentences. In every transcript, common ideas are grouped together and are assigned a name (the “code”). Different codes might have similar ideas but are not major enough to be considered a theme. To aid in identifying possible codes, the theoretical framework will be utilized, comprising Locus of Control (Rotter, 1966, as cited by Inoubli, 2024), Entrepreneurial Event Model (Shapero & Sokol, 1982, as cited by Inoubli, 2024), and Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991, as cited by Inoubli, 2024). This stage allows researchers to rapidly identify and group similar experiences, motivations, and intentions without necessarily extrapolating themes yet. It is imperative that reliability in coding be maintained as failing to do so may lead to flawed interpretation of the results.

Phase 3. After identifying and labeling experiences by their nature, initial themes are generated by analyzing and observing similar characteristics between codes. The word “generate” is used instead of “discover” as it is in the researchers’ discretion to create themes based on the codes as they see fit. Unlike codes, themes are not underlying or hidden pieces of information; they are created, in light of the researcher's own biases, assumptions, or preconceptions, as a central organizing concept. At this point, the researchers may now determine whether certain motivations, challenges, or intentions impact the overall lived experience more greatly than others.

Phase 4. Cleaning up and refining the themes is often necessary as some themes may not adequately reflect the interrelationships between the variables. Similar to quality

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control, in this phase, themes might be split into smaller sub-themes, merged into a more encompassing theme, or removed altogether. This process ensures the themes are rigorous. To conduct this, the researchers may either scrutinize each theme individually for any flaws, or look across them for any logical inconsistencies or if they make sense with respect to the goal of the study.

Phase 5. After recognizing the generated themes, naming and defining them is the next logical step. The researchers provide a name and a brief description for each theme. Aside from this, the researchers define boundaries as to what this theme is, and what it is not. However, if at this stage the themes are still not satisfactory to the researchers, Phase 4 can be repeated until finality is achieved. In this step, the researchers aim to clearly describe how different circumstances shape the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs.

Phase 6. Lastly, a write-up is conducted. The results, along with the themes, are organized and compiled into a well-structured report that provides a concise, critical interpretation of the findings (Braun & Clarke, 2021). It will provide a detailed explanation of each theme, with quotations from transcripts providing additional context, as well as what implications this theme will have in the lived experiences of SRSTHS student entrepreneurs. This approach will ensure a systematic, reliable, and meaningful analysis of qualitative data, which significantly advances the research on student entrepreneurship in the less-explored school environments: junior high school and science high schools.

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CHAPTER IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This section of the study presents the analysis of the data gathered regarding the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School (SRSTHS). Quotes from the data gathered, as well as related literature, are also included to support the researchers' interpretation. The individual responses were then presented to provide a clear and complete summary of the overall findings in this chapter. The study was divided into different segments according to the tabulated data.

RQ 1. What are the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?

This question delves into the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS, aiming to uncover how entrepreneurship affects their day-to-day lives. It includes how students describe their experiences, as well as whether engaging in entrepreneurship has positively or negatively influenced their lives.

Table 1

Annotated Responses to Research Question 1, Interview Question 1

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	My experience so far in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School since grade 7 is, I would say, very strict. Mostly, my businesses are [student-created materials]. When my students or classmates are	The participant exhibited hesitation in answering.

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	<p>having a hard time in their projects, they just ask me to draw. And so far, what I can say is that they are very strict on that policy, especially the [student-created materials].</p> <p>From what I've researched in school rule books, what I've seen is that there are no true rules that prohibit the sale of [student-created materials]. So that's where I have a problem in selling [student-created materials]. I also have a problem with that because many [figure of authority] say that it's prohibited when it's not stated in the rule book or even in any law in the DepEd.</p> <p>They say that it's prohibited to sell the [student-created materials], not the modules that they give. Of course, it's not allowed to sell, but the [student-created materials], it's really hard since the [figure of authority] is very strict about that. That's also my biggest quota in my business.</p> <p><i>Note. Identifying information has been abstracted to protect participant confidentiality.</i></p>	
Participant 2	<p>It's a rollercoaster ride. Mostly positive, since the people here are very welcoming for products. As long as you give them products that they are willing to buy and are not inherently a scam or low quality, then they will be really happy to pay and buy from you. And there are some rejections, of course. That is normal in selling stuff. But that is only a small percentage when you're selling to people.</p>	<p>The participant answered the question with confidence and enthusiasm.</p>
Participant 3	<p>For my experience, nakakapagod... 'pag minsan kasi, of course, pinagsasabay ko yung studies ko as well as yung business and 'pag minsan parang sobrang overwhelm na kasi nagsasabay-sabay. Tapos nandiyan yung... syempre, yung puyat, yung pagod, so, but syempre sa huli, it is rewarding naman.</p> <p><i>"For my experience, it's tiring because, of course, I</i></p>	<p>The participant was relaxed and composed while answering the question.</p>

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	<i>balance my studies as well as my business, and sometimes it becomes really overwhelming because everything happens at the same time. Then there's the lack of sleep, the exhaustion. But of course, in the end, it is rewarding."</i>	
Participant 4	So, I would describe my experiences as a student entrepreneur in SciTech is very fun, very exciting. There are many challenges that I have overcome. A part of them is losing profit, but I quickly regained money by selling the products to my fellow classmates, and yeah.	The participant was relaxed until the discussion shifted to more serious questions.
Participant 5	I think that it's fairly easy since when I first started selling, I was able to sell my entire batch. And later on, I tried selling other products, and I wasn't able to sell most of it. I think it's because of the price ranges, not everyone is able to afford it. And I guess that's what's been challenging for me.	The participant displayed an optimistic and encouraging attitude while answering the question.

Table 1 presents the annotated responses of the 5 participants to the interview question: *How would you describe your experiences as a student entrepreneur in SRSTHS?* The participants shared both the rewarding and demanding aspects of fulfilling entrepreneurial and academic obligations. Most participants stated difficulties in managing academics while dealing with profit gains and losses, as their side hustles sometimes caused exhaustion and distraction. One participant also highlighted institutional and operational challenges, particularly restrictions and unclear school policies that limited business activities despite existing demands.

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Notwithstanding these challenges, all participants expressed satisfaction with their entrepreneurial involvement, describing it as rewarding and a source of happiness. The researchers also observed that while participants displayed different emotions during the discussion, none showed signs of discomfort.

Specifically, Participant 1 described feeling confused and restricted due to ambiguous rules regarding his side hustle. On the other hand, Participant 2 characterized the experience as a rollercoaster while leaning towards optimism. Participant 3 emphasized the impact on academic performance, yet still found the experience rewarding. Similarly, Participant 4 also expressed optimism despite financial losses, believing perseverance could recover profits. Lastly, Participant 5 initially found the business easy but later felt challenged in expanding it.

These results imply that although student entrepreneurship could become an extensive strain on time and energy, it additionally provides worthwhile opportunities for skill development and financial independence. This contrasting nature of reward and demand is perceived to be inherent to the student entrepreneurial experience, emphasizing the need for a balancing act to achieve both academic and entrepreneurial success.

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Thematic Chart A

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“And there are some rejections, of course. That is normal in selling stuff. But that is only a small percentage when you're selling to people.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“But syempre sa huli, it is rewarding naman.”</p> <p>“<i>But of course, in the end, it is rewarding.</i>” – <i>Participant 3</i></p> <p>“So, I would describe my experiences as a student entrepreneur in SciTech is very fun, very exciting. There are many challenges that I have overcome. A part of them is losing profit, but I quickly regained money by selling the products to my fellow classmates, and yeah.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>	<p>Positive Attitude toward Entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Affective Experiences</p>
<p>“From what I've researched in school rule books, what I've seen is that there are no true rules that prohibit the sale of reviewers or any studying material that is used before exams. So that's where I have a problem in selling reviewers and also in art. I also have a problem with that because many teachers say that it's prohibited when it's not stated in the rule book or even in any law in the DepEd.” - <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“For my experience, nakakapagod... ‘pag minsan kasi, of course, pinagsasabay ko yung studies ko as well as yung business and ‘pag minsan parang sobrang overwhelm na kasi nagsasabay-sabay. Tapos nandiyan yung... syempre, yung puyat, yung pagod.”</p>	<p>Perceived Stress</p>	

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<p><i>“For my experience, it’s tiring because, of course, I balance my studies as well as my business, and sometimes it becomes really overwhelming because everything happens at the same time. Then there’s the lack of sleep, the exhaustion.”</i> – Participant 3</p> <p>“There are many challenges that I have overcome. A part of them is losing profit.” – Participant 4</p> <p>“And later on, I tried selling other products, and I wasn't able to sell most of it. I think it's because of the price ranges, not everyone is able to afford it. And I guess that's what's been challenging for me.” – Participant 5</p>		
<p>“It's a rollercoaster ride. Mostly positive, since the people here are very welcoming for products. As long as you give them products that they are willing to buy and are not inherently a scam or low quality, then they will be really happy to pay and buy from you. And there are some rejections, of course. That is normal in selling stuff. But that is only a small percentage when you're selling to people.” – Participant 2</p> <p>“So, I would describe my experiences as a student entrepreneur in SciTech is very fun, very exciting. There are many challenges that I have overcome. A part of them is losing profit, but I quickly regained money by selling the products to my fellow classmates, and yeah.” – Participant 4</p> <p>“For my experience, nakakapagod... ‘pag minsan kasi, of course, pinagsasabay ko yung studies ko as well as yung business and ‘pag</p>	<p>Fluctuating Emotions</p>	

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<p>minsang parang sobrang overwhelm na kasi nagsasabay-sabay. Tapos nandiyan yung... syempre, yung puyat, yung pagod, so, but syempre sa huli, it is rewarding naman.”</p> <p><i>“For my experience, it’s tiring because, of course, I balance my studies as well as my business, and sometimes it becomes really overwhelming because everything happens at the same time. Then there’s the lack of sleep, the exhaustion. But of course, in the end, it is rewarding.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p> <p>“I think that it's fairly easy since when I first started selling, I was able to sell my entire batch. And later on, I tried selling other products, and I wasn't able to sell most of it. I think it's because of the price ranges, not everyone is able to afford it. And I guess that's what's been challenging for me.”</p> <p>– Participant 5</p>	
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Thematic Chart A analyzes the responses regarding the overall experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS, revealing a superordinate theme of *Affective Experiences*. The data show that participants had varied experiences while working through the entrepreneurial field as students, which influenced how they perceive entrepreneurship. These experiences include both the challenging and rewarding aspects of running a business while attending formal classes. Student entrepreneurship was seen as more than a side hustle or a leisure activity; it affected well-being and tested character, with participants often treating each situation—positive or negative—as a chance to learn and grow.

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For instance, Participant 2 explicitly described the experience as a “rollercoaster ride,” sharing both the struggles and the ways they stayed positive. Similarly, other respondents perceived challenges as opportunities to advance and improve their entrepreneurial skills. Participant 1, on the other hand, faced moral dilemmas caused by unclear rules, which did not contradict with his personal ethics but conflicted with expectations from figures of authority. These responses show that student entrepreneurship can be both stressful and fulfilling, depending on circumstances and how students respond to obstacles.

The first subordinate theme is *positive attitude towards entrepreneurship*. This concept is associated with the entrepreneurial mindset of being goal-driven, adaptive, innovative, and resourceful as described by Somers (2022). Within this theme, the participants showed initiative and confidence in their abilities. Even when facing setbacks, they remained determined, adaptable, and willing to take risks, moving forward despite uncertainty.

The second subordinate theme is *perceived stress*, which is a common complex and subjective phenomenon in entrepreneurship, as stated by Kipkosgei (2022). All of the participants stated that stress caused by the unpredictable and demanding nature of entrepreneurship affects both schoolwork and business commitments. Although the process was challenging, these experiences also aided students to build resilience and perseverance.

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The final subordinate theme is *fluctuating emotions*, described by Portocorrero et al. (2025) as “affect spin.” Students experienced shifts in mood due to the vulnerable, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) environment, yet they were able to manage their emotions, stay motivated, and keep engaging with their entrepreneurial activities.

Therefore, the analysis indicates that student entrepreneurship generates a mix of emotions from the displeasure to pleasure spectrum. The participants demonstrated resilience, adaptability, and a learning mindset, showing that entrepreneurship can be both demanding and rewarding while offering important personal growth opportunities in the high school setting.

Table 2

Annotated Responses to Research Question 1, Interview Question 2

Participants	Responses	Researcher’s Observation
Participant 1	Since my family is not very well-off, entrepreneurship is what helps me with my allowance. Especially since I don't get paid every day or I don't get an allowance every month. It's very important for me to have commissions and orders from my classmates, from someone I know, even friends of a friend. It's important for me because I also need to budget especially since there are a lot of projects that the teachers are asking me to do. And the allowance that my parents give me is not enough. So entrepreneurship is very important for me, especially in this school.	The participant initially started with a gloomy tone, then showed an optimistic demeanor eventually.
Participant 2	Okay. So, in my daily life, you have to account for the	The

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	<p>time you're making your products and the time you're also going to sell those products. For my schedule, I usually sell them around lunch break. And I go home early so that I can produce my products and I can sell them the day after. And it has affected my daily lifestyle since my schedule is becoming more full and I'm being more occupied. But there is no negative effect since I am gaining money from it and passive income.”</p>	<p>participant’s confidence in answering questions remains consistent.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Ayon, ano, mayroong times na... for example, maraming need gawing school works tapos sasabay yung sa business ko like maraming need na gawin... Yeah, tapos syempre mapupuyat ta’s school kinabukasan, maapektuhan performance mo sa school kasi walang tulog tapos pagod.</p> <p><i>“There are times when, for example, there are many school works to do and then my business tasks also pile up. There are many things that need to be done. Yeah, and of course, I end up sleeping late, then I have school the next day. It affects my performance in school because I have no sleep, and I’m tired.”</i></p>	<p>The participant’s demeanor did not change at all; she still displayed a composed and relaxed manner in answering questions.</p>
Participant 4	<p>In a way that entrepreneurship affected my daily life as a student is that when I was trying to sell out my products and it affected what I said on my groupings because I forgot to cooperate or to contribute in our specific group activities because I was trying to sell my products in school, so yeah.</p>	<p>The participant's tone shifted into disappointment while answering this interview question.</p>
Participant 5	<p>I don't think that entrepreneurship necessarily made my daily life any harder since the process of making my product isn't really that tedious. I think that it's really easy. And whenever I do make my product, I don't plan for it ahead of time. And I usually just do it whenever I feel like it.</p>	<p>The participant consistently showed enthusiasm and positive outlook in entrepreneurial</p>

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Table 2 presents the annotated responses of all participants to the interview question: *In what way has entrepreneurship affected your daily life as a student?* The responses were fairly dispersed, as each participant experienced different types of impacts, reflecting the varied ways entrepreneurship affected their daily lives. A considerable number of responses indicated that the impact was largely personal, influenced by the demands of their environment and the additional responsibilities involved in managing a business alongside their studies.

Despite these differences, upon closer analysis, recurring codes and patterns emerged across individual responses. Specifically, Participants 1 and 2 leaned more toward the convenience aspect, particularly in terms of monetary gain from their entrepreneurial activities, while Participants 3 and 4 placed greater emphasis on the pressure it imposed on their academic performance. Although Participant 5 expressed a perspective distinct from the rest, it still demonstrated a similar sense of convenience consistent with that of Participants 1 and 2.

Across most responses, participants acknowledged the pressures and challenges that come with balancing entrepreneurial and academic obligations simultaneously. In addition to this, they also recognized the difficulty of managing personal and professional demands without compromising their well-being or other areas of responsibility. Throughout the discussion, all participants shared their experiences openly and

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consistently, with no signs of discomfort observed. Taken together, the responses suggest that student entrepreneurship can bring both practical benefits and academic pressures, with the extent of each varying according to the individual circumstances of the student.

Thematic Chart B

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“And it has affected my daily lifestyle since my schedule is becoming more full and I'm being more occupied.” – Participant 2</p> <p>“Ayon, ano, mayroong times na... for example, maraming need gawing school works tapos sasabay yung sa business ko like maraming need na gawin...”</p> <p><i>“There are times when, for example, there are many school works to do and then my business tasks also pile up. There are many things that need to be done.”</i> – Participant 3</p>	<p>Time Management Constraints</p>	<p>Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management</p>
<p>“Yeah, tapos syempre mapupuyat ta’s school kinabukasan, maaapektuhan performance mo sa school kasi walang tulog tapos pagod.”</p> <p><i>“Yeah, and of course, I end up sleeping late, then I have school the next day. It affects my performance in school because I have no sleep, and I’m tired.”</i> – Participant 3</p> <p>“I was trying to sell out my products and it affected what I said on my groupings because I</p>	<p>Impact on Academic Responsibilities</p>	

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<p>forgot to cooperate or to contribute in our specific group activities because I was trying to sell my products in school.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>		
<p>“And the allowance that my parents give me is not enough. So entrepreneurship is very important for me, especially in this school.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“But there is no negative effect since I am gaining money from it and passive income.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p>	<p>Financial Independence</p>	<p>Financial Empowerment and Autonomy</p>
<p>“I don't think that entrepreneurship necessarily made my daily life any harder since the process of making my product isn't really that tedious. I think that it's really easy. And whenever I do make my product, I don't plan for it ahead of time. And I usually just do it whenever I feel like it.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Perceived Manageability of Entrepreneurship</p>	

Thematic Chart B analyzes the impact of entrepreneurship on students, looking into how their personal and academic lives are affected by their involvement in entrepreneurial activities. Upon identifying the subordinate themes, two superordinate themes emerged: *Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management* and *Financial Empowerment and Autonomy*. The data showed that although the responses varied from one another, similarities could still be established by looking at the perspective through which participants viewed their experiences. Further analysis revealed that the responses carried implicit references to both the convenience and inconvenience that being a student entrepreneur brings into one's life.

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Some participants expressed a sense of financial independence, often setting aside the challenges they experienced because the monetary reward that came after served as motivation to continue. On the other hand, most participants found it difficult to manage tasks due to the buildup of activities and responsibilities, while one participant viewed entrepreneurship as manageable and without a negative impact on their daily life.

The first subordinate theme under *Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management* is *time management constraints*. Few entrepreneurs are always able to make efficient use of their time, with the assumption that the more effectively they manage it, the more they develop both their ventures and their personal lives. As stated by Skryhun and Nyzhnyk (2022), time in business is limited in the same way that time for other commitments is limited, making it crucial for entrepreneurs. In the process of selling, there are peak periods for customers and other business-related demands, making it a matter of what one chooses to prioritize first. For some participants, this led to distractions and fatigue which affected their performance in other areas of their lives, particularly academics.

The second subordinate theme is *impact on academic responsibilities*. Since the participants are student entrepreneurs, there is a direct impact on how they balance a business and their studies, given that both are demanding in nature. According to the NeuroLeadership Institute (2023), multitasking can significantly affect students, and based on scientific evidence, it is not possible for multitasking to happen without compromising the quality of at least one task. It not only impedes performance but also

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eventually disrupts cognitive function. This was reflected in the responses, as participants stated that managing both obligations at the same time is difficult, that one will always end up being set aside for the other, and that this also added to their stress levels.

The second superordinate theme, *Financial Empowerment and Autonomy*, encapsulates how entrepreneurship has been perceived by the respondents mostly through the rewards they receive.

The first subordinate theme under this is *financial independence*. As stated by Sylva and Nnena (2025), financial independence is what motivates innovators and entrepreneurs to become more creative, more driven, and more resourceful. The gain in status or monetary return provides a sense of gratification for progress and contributes to self-fulfillment, along with an increased sense of autonomy. This was consistent with the responses, as participants stated that with income from their own ventures, they have the freedom to purchase what they need and support themselves, especially when their allowance or socioeconomic status falls short.

The second subordinate theme is *perceived manageability of entrepreneurship*. As stated by Shah et al. (2023), perceived ease can serve as one of the motivational factors that contribute to someone pursuing a business, as they find it manageable to do, resulting in less stress and a sense of fulfillment in the process. This was mostly reflected in Participant 5's response, where the work was described as neither tedious nor demanding. For this participant, fulfillment from entrepreneurship remained a reason to continue.

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Therefore, the findings from Thematic Chart B indicate that the impact of entrepreneurship on students is not one-sided but rather falls along a spectrum between convenience and challenge. While some students viewed their entrepreneurial activities as a source of financial independence and fulfillment, others experienced strain in managing competing academic and entrepreneurial demands. Despite these differences, the responses collectively suggest that the experience of student entrepreneurship is determined by how each individual perceives and responds to the demands placed on them. Whether entrepreneurship is seen as a burden or a benefit depends on the student's ability to manage their responsibilities, their reasons for pursuing business, and the degree of ease and satisfaction they find in their entrepreneurial activities.

Table 3

Annotated Responses to Research Question 1, Interview Question 3

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	Yes, in a way, I did think of entrepreneurship making my life easier. Especially since I have a lot of connections in the school and also a friend of a friend who orders me art commissions since I have a skill to offer. So it did make my life easier, especially if the budget they give me is big to sell my products. So it's very helpful for me, it made my life easier. Especially since, as I said, my allowance is not that big. Yes [referring to making life harder], especially in SciTech. Since there are a lot of rules that the [figure of authority] don't want the [student-created materials] to sell. It's hard for me and sometimes, I will be very	The participant displayed excitement at first then became serious the second.

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	<p>honest, I just [manage it discreetly] so that I can have an allowance or money that I can use for the day or even for the whole week, depending on the budget or price they give me.</p> <p><i>Note. Identifying information has been abstracted to protect participant confidentiality.</i></p>	
Participant 2	<p>So, it's both. Harder because, well, you have to actually do it so that you can gain money. Easier because I am one of the few students in this batch that are not given a daily allowance that's enough for, for example, going out with friends or eating out. And I am only given the amount that I need for, for example, transportation. So, it has made my life easier since it was easier for me to contribute into projects since the money I make, I can use to give a bag, our bags. And I can also go out with friends and it has been a very entertaining experience.</p>	<p>The participant expressed his thoughts casually with pondering eyes.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Ano... actually both siya eh. It made my life easier in terms of alam mo yung 'pag may need ka may makukuha kang... ay, may mapagkukuhanan kang pera..</p> <p>Extra, yeah, extra money... like for example, may gusto kang, may nakita kang gusto mong bilhin like mabibili mo siya kasi may naipon ka from your business. So, it made my life harder naman kasi syempre at a young age dapat ang focus is studies. Most of your time dapat nasa studies pero since sinasabay yung sa business, nahahati yung oras ko. And syempre other extracurriculars pa. So, parang like mahirap pagsabayin. Na...challenging tapos yung time at ayon pagod.</p> <p><i>“Actually, it's both. It made my life easier in terms of when you need something, you have a source of money. Yes, extra money. For example, if you see something you want to buy, you can buy it because you've saved money from your business. It made my</i></p>	<p>The participant still answered calmly but occurrences of contemplation happened mid-sentences.</p>

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	<i>life harder because, at a young age, your focus should be on your studies. Most of your time should be for studying, but since I'm also managing a business, my time is divided. And of course, there are extracurricular activities too. So, it's hard to balance."</i>	
Participant 4	In times that I would tell entrepreneurship has made my life easier is that when I have earned enough money to buy gifts and to buy stuff for myself especially and to actually help my parents. And there's also a time that entrepreneurship has made my life harder because I was falling behind in school since I cannot contribute to specific activities. And yeah, so since I can't contribute in the group activities, my grades lowered or decreased for the past quarter and that's what entrepreneurship made my life harder.	The participant retained seriousness in answering the question.
Participant 5	I don't think that entrepreneurship has made my life harder since, again, I do not make products every day. So because of that, I still have time to do things that I actually want, and I still have time to do assignments and academic-related stuff.	The participant's tone and expression remained lively and congenial.

Table 3 presents the annotated responses of all participants to the interview question: *Are there times when you tell yourself, "entrepreneurship has made my life easier/harder"? Explain.* The responses showed that participants experienced both sides of entrepreneurship, with most of them acknowledging that it simultaneously brought convenience and difficulty into their lives. A common pattern among the responses was the dual nature of their experiences, where entrepreneurship provided financial relief on one hand but introduced academic and personal pressure on the other.

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Particularly, Participants 1, 2, 3, and 4 all described entrepreneurship as both making their lives easier and harder, though the weight they placed on each side differed. Participants 1 and 2 leaned more toward the convenience side, as both expressed that entrepreneurship served as a means to supplement their limited allowance and cover daily expenses. Participants 3 and 4, while also recognizing the financial benefit, placed more emphasis on how entrepreneurship made their lives harder, particularly in terms of divided attention and declining academic performance. Participant 5, however, stood apart from the rest, as this participant did not perceive entrepreneurship as making life harder at all, stating that the workload was infrequent enough to allow time for academics and personal activities.

Among the responses, participants consistently pointed to financial gain as the primary factor that made entrepreneurship convenient, while the toll it placed on academics and time management was identified as the primary source of difficulty. Throughout the discussion, all participants shared their experiences openly and consistently, with no signs of discomfort observed. As a whole, the responses suggest that the impact of student entrepreneurship on whether it makes life easier or harder is not fixed but rather depends on the frequency of entrepreneurial activities, the financial needs of the student, and their capacity to manage competing obligations.

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Thematic Chart C

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“So it did make my life easier, especially if the budget they give me is big to sell my products. So it's very helpful for me, it made my life easier. Especially since, as I said, my allowance is not that big.” <i>– Participant 1</i></p> <p>“So, it has made my life easier since it was easier for me to contribute into projects since the money I make, I can use to give a bag, our bags. And I can also go out with friends and it has been a very entertaining experience.” <i>– Participant 2</i></p> <p>“It made my life easier in terms of when you need something, you have a source of money. “Extra, yeah, extra money... like for example, may gusto kang, may nakita kang gusto mong bilhin like mabibili mo siya kasi may naipon ka from your business.”</p> <p><i>“Yes, extra money. For example, if you see something you want to buy, you can buy it because you’ve saved money from your business.”</i> <i>– Participant 3</i></p> <p>“In times that I would tell entrepreneurship has made my life easier is that when I have earned enough money to buy gifts and to buy stuff for myself especially and to actually help my parents.” <i>– Participant 4</i></p> <p>“I don't think that entrepreneurship has made my life harder since, again, I do not make</p>	<p>Positive Attitude toward Entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Affective Experiences</p>

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<p>products every day. So because of that, I still have time to do things that I actually want, and I still have time to do assignments and academic-related stuff.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>		
<p>“It's hard for me and sometimes, I will be very honest, I just do it in secret. I just do it behind the teacher's back so that I can have an allowance or money that I can use for the day or even for the whole week, depending on the budget or price they give me.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p>	<p>Perceived Stress</p>	
<p>“So it did make my life easier, especially if the budget they give me is big to sell my products. So it's very helpful for me, it made my life easier. Especially since, as I said, my allowance is not that big [...] It's hard for me and sometimes, I will be very honest, I just do it in secret. I just do it behind the teacher's back so that I can have an allowance or money that I can use for the day or even for the whole week, depending on the budget or price they give me.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“So, it's both. Harder because, well, you have to actually do it so that you can gain money. Easier because I am one of the few students in this batch that are not given a daily allowance that's enough for, for example, going out with friends or eating out.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“Ano... actually both siya eh. It made my life easier in terms of alam mo yung ‘pag may need ka may makukuha kang... ay, may mapagkukuhanan kang pera.. Extra, yeah, extra money... like for example, may gusto kang, may nakita kang gusto mong</p>	<p>Fluctuating Emotions</p>	

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<p>bilhin like mabibili mo siya kasi may naipon ka from your business. So, it made my life harder naman kasi syempre at a young age dapat ang focus is studies.”</p> <p><i>“Actually, it’s both. It made my life easier in terms of when you need something, you have a source of money. Yes, extra money. For example, if you see something you want to buy, you can buy it because you’ve saved money from your business. It made my life harder because, at a young age, your focus should be on your studies.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p> <p>“In times that I would tell entrepreneurship has made my life easier is that when I have earned enough money to buy gifts and to buy stuff for myself especially and to actually help my parents. And there's also a time that entrepreneurship has made my life harder because I was falling behind in school since I cannot contribute to specific activities.”</p> <p>– Participant 4</p>		
<p>“And I am only given the amount that I need for, for example, transportation. So, it has made my life easier since it was easier for me to contribute into projects since the money I make, I can use to give a bag, our bags. And I can also go out with friends and it has been a very entertaining experience.”</p> <p>– Participant 2</p> <p>“Ano... actually both siya eh. It made my life easier in terms of alam mo yung ‘pag may need ka may makukuha kang... ay, may mapagkukuhanan kang pera.. Extra, yeah, extra money... like for example, may gusto kang, may nakita kang gusto mong bilhin like mabibili mo siya kasi may naipon ka</p>	<p>Financial Independence</p>	<p>Financial Empowerment and Autonomy</p>

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<p>from your business.”</p> <p><i>“Actually, it’s both. It made my life easier in terms of when you need something, you have a source of money. Yes, extra money. For example, if you see something you want to buy, you can buy it because you’ve saved money from your business.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p>		
<p>“I don't think that entrepreneurship has made my life harder since, again, I do not make products every day. So because of that, I still have time to do things that I actually want, and I still have time to do assignments and academic-related stuff.”</p> <p>– Participant 5</p>	<p>Perceived Manageability of Entrepreneurship</p>	
<p>“So, it made my life harder naman kasi syempre at a young age dapat ang focus is studies. Most of your time dapat nasa studies pero since sinasabay yung sa business, nahahati yung oras ko. And syempre other extracurriculars pa. So, parang like mahirap pagsabayin.”</p> <p><i>“It made my life harder because, at a young age, your focus should be on your studies. Most of your time should be for studying, but since I’m also managing a business, my time is divided. And of course, there are extracurricular activities too. So, it’s hard to balance.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p>	<p>Time Management Constraints</p>	<p>Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management</p>

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<p>“And there's also a time that entrepreneurship has made my life harder because I was falling behind in school since I cannot contribute to specific activities. And yeah, so since I can't contribute in the group activities, my grades lowered or decreased for the past quarter and that's what entrepreneurship made my life harder.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>	<p>Impact on Academic Responsibilities</p>	
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Thematic Chart C looks at how student entrepreneurship has made the lives of participants easier or harder, covering the emotional, financial, and academic sides of their experiences. After identifying the subordinate themes, three superordinate themes emerged: *Affective Experiences*, *Financial Empowerment and Autonomy*, and *Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management*. The data indicated that while participants had different takes on the matter, there were still connections that could be drawn based on how they measured the benefits in contrast to the downsides of being a student entrepreneur. What became apparent through further analysis was that the responses reflected a constant push and pull between the rewards and pressures that entrepreneurship brought into their routines.

Most participants recognized that entrepreneurship made their lives both easier and harder at the same time. The convenience was largely connected to the financial returns they earned, which helped them cover personal expenses and sustain themselves outside of what their allowance could offer. However, this came at a cost, as running a business alongside academic and extracurricular responsibilities created pressure that

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interfered with their focus and output. One participant, however, did not share this experience, viewing entrepreneurship as light enough to maintain balance between business and academics.

The superordinate theme, *Affective Experiences*, deals with the ways participants' emotions and behaviors respond to different situations, influencing their motivation, focus, and emotional reactions ranging from stress to satisfaction.

The first subordinate theme is *positive attitude towards entrepreneurship*. The adoption of an entrepreneurial mindset of being proactive and resourceful (Somers, 2022). In the case of Participant 1, despite the restrictions set within the school environment, the participant still found ways to sell products even if it meant doing so discreetly. Instead of being discouraged by the limitations, the participant stayed determined and resourceful, treating the monetary reward as reason enough to keep going with entrepreneurial activities.

The second subordinate theme is *perceived stress*, a common, complex, and subjective phenomenon in entrepreneurship (Kipkosgei, 2022). This surfaced in the responses of Participants 1, 2, 3, and 4, all of whom described entrepreneurship as making their lives harder in one way or another. Participant 1 spoke about the difficulty of operating under restrictions, Participant 2 pointed out the effort needed just to earn money, Participant 3 brought up how focus should be on studies yet entrepreneurship splits that focus, and Participant 4 directly connected business involvement to falling behind in school. While the process was described as difficult, these experiences also

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show how students gradually developed tolerance toward the pressures that come with running a business.

The final subordinate theme is *fluctuating emotions*, the quick shift in emotional responses according to their environment (Portocorrero et al., 2025). This came through in the responses of Participants 2 and 3, where both talked about entrepreneurship making their lives easier and harder at the same time. Participant 2 found the experience both demanding and entertaining, while Participant 3 appreciated the financial convenience but also felt the weight of balancing responsibilities at a young age. These shifts between positive and negative perceptions within a single response further emphasizes the uncertain and ambiguous nature of student entrepreneurship, yet both participants still continued engaging with their businesses despite these emotional shifts.

The second superordinate theme, *Financial Empowerment and Autonomy*, covers how manageable or beneficial entrepreneurship has been for the students, which is largely reflected through the financial rewards and sense of ease they experienced.

The first subordinate theme under this is *financial independence*. Sylva and Nnena (2025) stated that financial independence motivates entrepreneurs to be more creative, motivated, and resourceful. This is parallel with the responses, as participants who felt entrepreneurship made their lives easier pointed to financial rewards as the reason. Participant 1 cited a limited allowance as the reason entrepreneurship helped, Participant 2 talked about being able to chip in for school projects and go out with friends, Participant 3 referred to having extra money to buy what is needed, and

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Participant 4 mentioned that earnings went toward purchasing gifts and helping parents. In each instance, the income from their ventures gave them a level of financial freedom that their allowance alone could not provide.

The second subordinate theme is *perceived manageability of entrepreneurship*. As stated by Shah et al. (2023), perceived ease can serve as one of the motivational factors that lead someone to pursue a business, as they consider it doable, resulting in less stress and a sense of fulfillment in the process. This was seen in Participant 5's response, where entrepreneurship was not viewed as making life harder because products were not made on a daily basis. This gave the participant enough room for academics and personal interests, making entrepreneurship something that fit into daily life rather than something that disrupted it.

Lastly, the third superordinate theme, *Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management*, addresses the tension between academic and entrepreneurial obligations and the pressure of figuring out what to prioritize.

The first subordinate theme identified is *time management constraints*. As stated by Skryhun and Nyzhnyk (2022), time in business is limited in the same way that time for other commitments is limited, making it a matter of what one decides to put first. This was present in Participant 3's response, where the participant mentioned that time is divided between studies, business, and extracurricular activities, making it hard to keep up with all three. The participant also brought up fatigue as a result of trying to juggle

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these competing demands, reinforcing that time, as a limited resource, only gets tighter when divided between multiple obligations.

The second subordinate theme is *impact on academic responsibilities*. According to the NeuroLeadership Institute (2023), multitasking can significantly affect students, and based on scientific evidence, it is not possible for multitasking to happen without compromising the quality of at least one task. This was present in Participant 4's response, where the participant said that grades went down because of the inability to contribute to group activities due to business commitments. The participant associated entrepreneurship directly with falling behind in school, indicating that when business demands go up, academic responsibilities tend to get the latter effect.

Therefore, the findings from Thematic Chart C indicate that the answers to whether student entrepreneurship affects the respondents' lives lies along a spectrum encompassing emotional, financial, and academic dimensions. While financial independence and perceived manageability made entrepreneurship work for some, the emotional weight and competing academic demands made it a struggle for others. The responses holistically point to the idea that student entrepreneurs are always weighing the rewards against the pressures of what they do, and how each respondent deals with this depends on their financial situation, how often they engage in entrepreneurial activities, and how well they handle the emotional and academic demands that come along with it.

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RQ 2. What are the different motivations of SRSTHS students for pursuing student entrepreneurship?

This question explores the different motivations SRSTHS students have for pursuing student entrepreneurship. It includes the importance of these motivations in driving students to pursue entrepreneurship and how they affect both the students' daily lives and entrepreneurial performance.

Table 4

Annotated Responses to Research Question 2, Interview Question 1

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	For me, the thing that motivates me the most is money. Since I really need money for everyday school life and also sometimes even just leisure activities with friends. So that I won't be too busy with my studies and also have time for myself to have fun. That's why it's very important for me to become a student entrepreneur.	The participant was serious and sure of her answer.
Participant 2	What motivates me is the experience I gained. So, the experience I gained from interacting with different people of different grade levels is invaluable since I get to see their facial reactions, their body languages, how they react on how I talk to them. And it has also made my speaking more fluent since it will be harder to buy [from] someone who can't speak properly, right? And at the same time, the money that I gain from it goes a long way and it has helped me in	It took the participant some time before answering the question.

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	achieving my academic goals as well as my leisurely goals.	
Participant 3	<p>What motivates me is yung thought na may sarili akong pera. Like I don't have to ask my parents... Yeah, for money like syempre mga wants ko I can buy it on my own like from the money from my business.</p> <p><i>“What motivates me is the thought that I have my own money. I don't have to ask my parents. Yes, for money. For example, my wants, I can buy them on my own using the money from my business.”</i></p>	The participant answered with no hesitation.
Participant 4	<p>What motivates me into becoming a student entrepreneur is to become an inspiration to other people or to other students that there's a free will in earning your own money because having your own money gives you free will on what you will buy.</p>	The participant took some time reflecting before answering.
Participant 5	<p>I guess something that motivates me in being a student entrepreneur is that I'm able to help my family since we're like that. I guess because I'm able to help them financially, even by just selling my products.</p>	The participant was calm when answering the question.

Table 4 shows the responses of the participants to the interview question: *What motivates you in being a student entrepreneur?* The motivating factors included financial needs, personal independence, gaining experience, inspiring others, and supporting family members. These reasons showed that in addition to financial gain, students may become entrepreneurs for social and personal reasons. The responses from the participants also demonstrated how engaging in entrepreneurial activities helped them gain leisure from their academic lives and develop a sense of purpose, responsibility, and confidence.

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Participants 1, 2 and 3 expressed that money was their main motivation to become student entrepreneurs, with Participant 2 adding that the experiences one gains is also one of their motivations. Participant 4 stated that being an inspiration for other students is what drove them to pursue entrepreneurship. Lastly, Participant 5 shared that being able to help their family is what motivated them.

Thematic Chart D

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“For me, the thing that motivates me the most is money.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“What motivates me is yung thought na may sarili akong pera. Like I don't have to ask my parents...”</p> <p>“<i>What motivates me is the thought that I have my own money. I don't have to ask my parents.</i>” – <i>Participant 3</i></p>	<p>Allowance Supplementation</p>	<p>Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship</p>
<p>“And at the same time, the money that I gain from it goes a long way and it has helped me in achieving my academic goals as well as my leisurely goals.” –<i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“What motivates me is yung thought na may sarili akong pera. Like I don't have to ask my parents...”</p>	<p>Financial Independence Aspirations</p>	

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<p>“What motivates me is the thought that I have my own money. I don’t have to ask my parents.” – Participant 3</p> <p>“What motivates me into becoming a student entrepreneur is to become an inspiration to other people or to other students that there's a free will in earning your own money because having your own money gives you free will on what you will buy.” – Participant 4</p>		
<p>“What motivates me is the experience I gained.” – Participant 2</p>	Experience Acquisition	
<p>“I guess something that motivates me in being a student entrepreneur is that I'm able to help my family since we're like that.” – Participant 5</p>	Household Financial Contribution	

Thematic Chart D centers on the superordinate theme ***Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship*** which explores the motivations of participants in engaging with student entrepreneurship. According to their responses, the participants were motivated by a combination of financial, personal, and experiential factors that encouraged them to start and maintain their businesses while studying. While earning money was seen as a major driving force in pursuing entrepreneurship, it was also found that other factors such as independence, personal growth, and financial contribution to their households were used by the participants as motivation.

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The first of the subordinate themes was *allowance supplementation*. This refers to the participants' motivation to earn more money to support their personal and academic needs. For instance, Participant 1 made it clear that money was their central motivation for pursuing entrepreneurship. In addition, Participant 2 also said that they became an entrepreneur to achieve various academic and leisure-oriented goals with their own money. From the information gathered, it is evident that entrepreneurship was seen as an additional source of income separate from their allowance that enabled participants to meet their expenses. This assertion is also supported by literature that suggests that income expectations and financial needs of students play an important role in their interest in entrepreneurship (Kuswanto et al., 2023).

The second subordinate theme, *financial independence aspirations*, describes the participants' desire to gain financial autonomy and reduce reliance on their parents. As stated by Participant 3, earning their own money allowed them to avoid asking their parents for financial support. This reflects a growing sense of independence and financial responsibility among the participants. Participant 4 also shared that they became a student entrepreneur to inspire others by showing that earning money independently is possible. This is consistent with the findings of Xanthopoulou & Sahinidis (2024), who stated that entrepreneurship aids in the development of financial management and literacy.

The third subordinate theme, *experience acquisition*, highlighted the participants' motivation to gain knowledge and practical experience through entrepreneurship. Participant 2 emphasized that business experience was a key motivating factor in their

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pursuit of entrepreneurship. Research supports that entrepreneurship offers practical learning opportunities that develop students’ skills, creativity, and innovation (Yang et al., 2024).

Lastly, the fourth subordinate theme is *household financial contribution*.

Participant 5 stated that helping their families became a motivating factor for becoming a student entrepreneur. In other words, it is clear that entrepreneurship was not only a means for personal gain but also a way to help their families. This is consistent with past studies that have shown how financial behavior and financial awareness could affect participants’ motivation to become entrepreneurs, especially if their purpose is to better their economic situations or help their families (Rapina et al., 2023).

Table 5

Annotated Responses to Research Question 2, Interview Question 2

Participants	Responses	Researcher’s Observation
Participant 1	Yes, it does make my life easier because even though there are a lot of rules, a lot of restrictions that the teachers give. This motivation, the money that motivates me, really pushes me to not give up even though there are a lot of restrictions that the teachers and my advisers give me. So even though there are restrictions, I try my best to at least bypass or find another way to sell a product that is not restricted or not prohibited.	The participant replied with no hesitation.
Participant 2	Okay. So, it makes my life easier in terms of how I live my life because if you set up motivations for	The participant took some time

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	<p>yourself in becoming an entrepreneur, then you'll become more goal-orientated as to say that you won't stray away from the path that you chose. And since you have a path that you chose, it's easy to make decisions in accordance to achieving that goal. So, for example, if I had my motivations to become an entrepreneur to gain money, to live comfortably, then I can make choices easier like, for example, getting a higher paying job. It's an easier choice for me instead of choosing my passion since I am motivated and I'm goal-oriented to follow that course.</p>	<p>to think before answering calmly.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Yeah, it makes my life easier. Wala kang naiisip na, hala, saan ako kukuha ng pera. Mayroon akong security na mayroon kang mapagkukuhanan.</p> <p><i>“Yes, it makes my life easier. You don’t think, “Oh no, where will I get money?” I have security that I have a source.”</i></p>	<p>The participant answered with confidence and humor.</p>
Participant 4	<p>Actually it teaches us on how to be independent or to learn how to budget our money and how to handle our finances as a young student.</p>	<p>The participant hesitated for a short while before answering.</p>
Participant 5	<p>I think somehow, yeah, it has made my life as an entrepreneur easier since they are also supportive of me selling my products at school, and they also help me to do budgeting and stuff like that. So I guess, they motivate me and it made my entrepreneur life easier.</p>	<p>The participant was somehow unsure how to answer the question before answering.</p>

Table 5 shows the responses of the participants to the interview question: *Do these motivations make your life as an entrepreneur easier? How so?* The responses showed that motivations helped participants handle their entrepreneurial duties better by

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giving them clear goals, persistence, and financial awareness. Most participants pointed out that having strong motivations kept them committed to their businesses, even though they experience challenges of being student entrepreneurs.

Participant 1 explained that financial motivation made their entrepreneurial life easier by encouraging them to keep selling, even when certain restrictions held them back. Participant 2 stated that motivation helped them stay goal-oriented, which made decision-making easier, enabling them to choose options that fit their long-term goals. Participant 3 stressed the financial security that entrepreneurship brought, stating that having a source of income eased their worries about money. Participant 4 highlighted how entrepreneurship taught them independence and proper financial management, especially in budgeting and handling finances at an early age. Finally, Participant 5 noted that support from family members motivated entrepreneurial activities and assisted in financial management.

Thematic Chart E

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“Yes, it does make my life easier because even though there are many rules and restrictions from teachers, the money that motivates me pushes me not to give up. I try to find other ways to sell products that are not restricted.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“Yeah, it makes my life easier. Wala kang</p>	<p>Financial Motivation and Security</p>	<p>Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship</p>

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<p>naiisip na, hala, saan ako kukuha ng pera. Mayroon akong security na mayroon kang mapagkukuhanan.”</p> <p><i>“Yes, it makes my life easier. You don’t think, ‘Where will I get money?’ because you have security that you have a source.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p>		
<p>“It makes my life easier because when you set motivations for yourself, you become more goal-oriented and it becomes easier to make decisions that align with your goals.”</p> <p>– Participant 2</p>	<p>Goal Orientation</p>	
<p>“It teaches us how to be independent and learn how to budget our money and handle our finances as a young student.”</p> <p>– Participant 4</p> <p>“It has made my life easier since they support me selling my products at school and help me with budgeting.”</p> <p>– Participant 5</p>	<p>Development of Independence and Financial Skills</p>	

Thematic Chart E shows that there is one superordinate theme that accounts for the role of motivations in the entrepreneurial experience and performance of the participants: ***Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship***. The responses highlighted how motivations such as their need for money, personal goals, and skill development, played a crucial role in helping the participants overcome the challenges and difficulties they faced. Previous studies have shown that motivational factors can play a significant role in enhancing entrepreneurial persistence and performance among

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students from a psychological point of view, as motivational factors can guide them in achieving their goals (Ryan & Deci, 2023).

The superordinate theme, *Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship*, manifested through subordinate themes such as *financial motivation and security, goal orientation*, and *development of independence and financial skills*.

These themes illustrated how motivation functioned as a driving force that supported the participants in sustaining their entrepreneurial activities and improving their personal development.

The first subordinate theme, *financial motivation and security*, related to the perception of entrepreneurship in terms of financial support and security. Participant 1 stated that financial motivation encouraged them to continue selling despite administrative restrictions. On the other hand, Participant 3 highlighted that having an income source made their life easier. These responses are in line with related literature that showed how important financial security was as a motivator in entrepreneurship (Fan et al., 2024).

The second subordinate theme, *goal orientation*, revealed how entrepreneurial motivations helped participants set personal and academic goals. Specifically, Participant 2 highlighted that through entrepreneurial motivation, they were able to set goals for entrepreneurship and academics. This corresponds with relevant literature which states that entrepreneurial motivation is responsible for goal orientation (Liñeiro et al., 2024).

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The third subordinate theme, *development of independence and financial skills*, highlighted how entrepreneurship helped participants build personal independence and improve their financial management abilities. Participant 4 noted that running a business taught them proper financial management while Participant 5 stated that through parental support, selling and budgeting was made a lot easier. These people are proof that entrepreneurship helps people develop skills by actually using money. This is supported by the study of Liñeiro et al. (2024), which stated that entrepreneurial engagement among students enhances their financial management skills, independence, and also their decision-making abilities, which is essential for long-term financial well-being.

Table 6

Annotated Responses to Research Question 2, Interview Question 3

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	For me, it's very important because as I've said, the restrictions can demotivate you to sell. It can be your way to reject the entrepreneurship life especially since part of the challenge is the restrictions of other people and especially the school in that type of business. But as I've said, we really need to think about the results especially for the students who are not well-off who are using their entrepreneurship as a way to have their own allowance.	The participant replied with confidence, emphasizing determination despite restrictions and the importance of financial support.
Participant 2	Okay, so let's dive into academic performance. So, if I have goals set up as an entrepreneur, they are important because if I can set up goals as an	The participant replied thoughtfully,

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	<p>entrepreneur, then I can set up goals as an academic student. I can set up goals where I want to be, like where I want to be in, for example, in graduation. I want to be this much. I want to achieve this much. So, having motivations generally, of course, as an entrepreneur as well, is a good thing since it gives you a direction on where you want to be in a time frame and it gives you the urgency to achieve those goals and have less hesitation on your decisions.</p>	<p>linking motivations to academic goals.</p>
Participant 3	<p>So, yung motivations na ‘yon syempre importante siya, kasi ayon yung reason bakit ko ipinagpapatuloy ang pagiging entrepreneur. So, having the thought na kumikita ako ng pera. Syempre, mas nagiging, mas gusto ko pang magpursigi kasi once na... na-experience mong kumita ng sarili mong pera, alam mo yung ‘di ka na makatigil kasi you want to move forward and gusto mo na lalo ka pang kumita.</p> <p><i>“Those motivations are important because they’re the reason why I continue being an entrepreneur. Having the thought that I earn money makes me want to strive harder. Once you experience earning your own money, you can’t stop. You want to move forward and earn even more.”</i></p>	<p>The participant replied enthusiastically, showing pride in earning money.</p>
Participant 4	<p>Those motivations help me continue becoming an entrepreneur and in overcoming challenges, especially in academics.</p>	<p>The participant replied calmly.</p>
Participant 5	<p>I guess another factor that motivates me in selling my products are the reactions of those who consume my product. And from the reactions, it makes me happy. They enjoy what I make. I guess I enjoy the fact that they like what I make.. They really like it. So I guess it makes me want to make more to make them happy. It makes me proud.</p>	<p>The participant replied positively, motivated by consumer reactions.</p>

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Table 6 presents the responses of participants regarding the interview question:

For you, how important are these motivations in pursuing entrepreneurship? How significantly do they affect your performance? Motivations are essential for maintaining entrepreneurial engagement, directing goal-setting, and boosting personal satisfaction. Participants said that motivations affected persistence and decision-making. Some participants connected it to emotional fulfillment, financial independence, or even academic achievements.

Participant 1 highlighted the value of financial assistance and tenacity in the face of adversity. Meanwhile, Participant 2 stated that motivations can help them set academic and entrepreneurial goals. Participant 3 took pride in making money, while Participant 4 remained indifferent to challenges. Lastly for participant 5, motivation from responses from customers and satisfaction was pointed out.

Thematic Chart F

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
“Those motivations help me continue becoming an entrepreneur and in overcoming challenges, especially in academics.” – <i>Participant 2</i>	Overcoming Obstacles	Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship
“For me, it's very important because as I've said, the restrictions can demotivate you to sell. It can be your way to reject the entrepreneurship life especially since part of the challenge is the restrictions of other people	Financial drive	

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<p>and especially the school in that type of business. But as I've said, we really need to think about the results especially for the students who are not well-off who are using their entrepreneurship as a way to have their own allowance.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“So, having the thought na kumikita ako ng pera. Syempre, mas nagiging, mas gusto ko pang magpursigi kasi once na... na-experience mong kumita ng sarili mong pera, alam mo yung ‘di ka na makatigil kasi you want to move forward and gusto mo na lalo ka pang kumita.”</p> <p><i>“Having the thought that I earn money makes me want to strive harder. Once you experience earning your own money, you can’t stop. You want to move forward and earn even more.”</i> – <i>Participant 3</i></p>		
<p>“I guess another factor that motivates me in selling my products are the reactions of those who consume my product. And from the reactions, it makes me happy. They enjoy what I make. I guess I enjoy the fact that they like what I make.. They really like it. So I guess it makes me want to make more to make them happy. It makes me proud.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Customer Feedback and Satisfaction</p>	
<p>“Okay, so let's dive into academic performance. So, if I have goals set up as an entrepreneur, they are important because if I can set up goals as an entrepreneur, then I can set up goals as an academic student. I can set up goals where I want to be, like where I want to be in, for example, in graduation.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p>	<p>Goal Orientation</p>	

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The results of the thematic analysis of Thematic Chart F show that there is one superordinate theme that describes the role of motivation in influencing the entrepreneurial experience and performance of the participants, and it is ***Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship***. The results of the study show that motivation plays an important role in encouraging student entrepreneurs to continue with their entrepreneurial activities and enhance their performance. The participants of the study identified their motivations, such as financial benefits, personal goals, satisfaction of customers, and perseverance despite the restrictions, as influencing their determination to continue with the sale of their products. These motivations are important in helping students stay focused and make better decisions in their entrepreneurship and academic lives. Research has shown that entrepreneurial motivation is a significant influencer of students' involvement and performance in entrepreneurial practices (Baliga & Gil, 2024, Widyaningrum et al., 2024).

The first subordinate theme, ***overcoming obstacles***, focuses on how student entrepreneurs are motivated to overcome obstacles through various challenges. Participant 2 emphasized how their motivations helped them overcome academic difficulties. Research has previously established that entrepreneurial motivation is crucial in helping entrepreneurs build resilience in dealing with challenges and obstacles (Jamil et al., 2024). These findings highlight the role of motivation in helping student entrepreneurs overcome obstacles and challenges.

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The second subordinate theme is *financial drive*, which describes how financial motivation enables students to work harder to enhance their entrepreneurial performance. Participant 1 stated that even though restrictions can sometimes be demotivating, financial benefits drove them to keep on with their entrepreneurial endeavors. Participant 3 also stated that earning money is what motivated them to continue pursuing entrepreneurship. Previous research has shown how financial incentives influence students' interest in entrepreneurship and motivate them to explore business opportunities (Septi et al., 2024). These findings highlight how financial gains play a major role as motivation for student entrepreneur's business activities.

The third subordinate theme is *customer feedback and satisfaction*, which emphasizes how customer feedback can serve as motivation for student entrepreneurs to continue their business. Participant 5 noted that seeing customer reactions and enjoyment gives them a sense of pride that drives them to make more products and continue their business. This shows that emotional satisfaction from customers can boost the motivation of student entrepreneurs in managing their business.

The last subordinate theme is *goal orientation*, which highlights how motivation assists student entrepreneurs in setting personal and academic goals. Participant 2 stated that by setting goals in entrepreneurship, the participant was also able to set academic goals. This shows that entrepreneurial motivation helped student entrepreneurs in forming systematic thoughts and plans. These findings are in line with related literature which indicates that goal-oriented individuals are likely to display high entrepreneurial

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intentions and success because they are driven to attain certain objectives (Jalal et al., 2024).

RQ 3. What are the different challenges faced by student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?

This question delves into the different challenges SRSTHS student entrepreneurs encounter and explores how they overcome them. It includes insights on how students handle these challenges and how it affects students’ daily lives outside of entrepreneurship.

Table 7

Annotated Responses to Research Question 3, Interview Question 1

Participants	Responses	Researcher’s Observation
Participant 1	As I've said, my challenges are the restrictions of the teachers and sometimes, my challenges are the deliveries especially in art commissions or even writing commissions to my friends from other schools. But my way to solve those challenges is that I just reach out to them. It's like they just pick up what I'm commissioning to them here in the school for better access and for the two of us to be more accessible to our customers.	The participant displayed a calm composure, with a hint of uncertainty.
Participant 2	Yes, [the] first challenge is time since it's very hard to look for time when you're in this school where academics matter a lot. Second is fatigue since we are tired every day from our academics. Then you have to	The participant appeared troubled when recalling the

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	<p>find that motivation somewhere or discipline that you need to get up and you need to do something. You need to accomplish your task. And finally, the actual creation of the products since you don't want to sell something that will harm your customers or will give them a bad feedback about you since that's bad for business. And as well as the actual selling part since, of course, I'm a one-man army. I don't have other people with me so I'm the one who sells. I'm the one who calculates the money and the change. I'm the one who makes the product. So, manpower is also a thing since I can only do so much by myself.</p>	<p>challenges they faced.</p>
<p>Participant 3</p>	<p>Unang-una sa time kasi as a student marami rin namang school activities tapos din mga extra curricular tapos mga personal na ginagawa ko. So, mahirap ipagkasiya lahat ng 'yon... knowing na limited lang ang time ko. Tapos andyan din yung paghanap mo ng customers kasi nga syempre wala ka masyadong oras parang 'di ka.. kasi dito sa school, as a mahiyain person mahirap kumuha ng costumers na bibili ng product mo kasi nahihya ako tapos wala rin ako masyadong kilala sa ibang section. So, 'pag minsan talaga matumal. Tapos sa labas naman ng school like 'di ka naman kasi makikilala ng ibang tao if 'di ka magpopost sa social media or 'di mo iieeganyo yung product mo. So kung limited lang ang time ko, parang limited lang din ang costumers ko. So, ayon mga challenges ko. Unang-una, yung limited time, limited production, [and] limited customers.</p> <p><i>“Yes. First is time, because as a student there are many school activities, extracurriculars, and personal things I do. It’s hard to fit everything in, knowing that my time is limited. Then there’s finding customers. Since I don’t have much time and here in school as a shy person, it’s hard to get customers to buy my product because I’m shy and I don’t know many people from other sections. So sometimes sales are slow. Outside of school, people won’t know you unless you post on social media or promote your product. If</i></p>	<p>The participant appeared contemplative but consistently answered with a calm demeanor.</p>

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	<i>my time is limited, my customers are also limited. So those are my challenges: limited time, limited production, and limited customers. ”</i>	
Participant 4	As a student entrepreneur, I do face challenges regarding my business because specifically sometimes I don't have enough profit to buy materials for my products so that I can't sell another batch of my products.	The participant was particularly gloomy and serious while answering.
Participant 5	I don't really face any challenges, especially since the product that I sell. I don't see any other students selling the same product as I do. So I think somehow it gave me an advantage that I'm selling something that's unique and other people also want.	The participant appears confident when answering.

Table 7 presents the responses of the participants regarding the interview question: *As a student entrepreneur, do you face any challenges regarding your businesses? How so?* The responses revealed that participants encountered several operational challenges while managing their businesses alongside their academic responsibilities. Most participants emphasized difficulties related to time management, production capacity, marketing their products, and meeting customer expectations. These challenges were often connected to balancing school requirements with entrepreneurial responsibilities. The researchers also observed varying emotional responses from the participants, ranging from calm reflection to visible concern when recalling the challenges they experienced.

Participant 1 expressed that restrictions from teachers and difficulties in arranging deliveries for commissions posed challenges, which they addressed by coordinating with

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customers for more accessible pick-up locations. Participant 2 highlighted time constraints, academic fatigue, and the responsibility of ensuring products were safe and of good quality, while also noting the difficulty of handling all aspects of the business alone. Participant 3 similarly pointed out that limited time and personal commitments affected production and customer reach, and that shyness and limited connections made marketing more difficult. Participant 4 discussed financial constraints, particularly the challenge of earning enough profit to purchase additional materials, while Participant 5 reported minimal challenges, noting that the uniqueness of their product gave them an advantage in the market.

Thematic Chart G

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“And as well as the actual selling part since, of course, I'm a one-man army. I don't have other people with me so I'm the one who sells. I'm the one who calculates the money and the change. I'm the one who makes the product. So, manpower is also a thing since I can only do so much by myself.” <i>– Participant 2</i></p> <p>“So, ayon mga challenges ko. Unang-una, yung limited time, limited production, [and] limited customers.”</p> <p><i>“So those are my challenges: limited time, limited production, and limited customers.”</i> <i>– Participant 3</i></p>	<p>Production Struggles</p>	<p>Operational Challenges and Competence Development</p>

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<p>“As a student entrepreneur, I do face challenges regarding my business because specifically sometimes I don't have enough profit to buy materials for my products so that I can't sell another batch of my products.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>		
<p>“And finally, the actual creation of the products since you don't want to sell something that will harm your customers or will give them a bad feedback about you since that's bad for business.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p>	<p>Customer Expectation Pressure</p>	
<p>“...My challenges are the deliveries especially in art commissions or even writing commissions to my friends from other schools. But my way to solve those challenges is that I just reach out to them. It's like they just pick up what I'm commissioning to them here in the school for better access and for the two of us to be more accessible to our customers.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“Yes, [the] first challenge is time since it's very hard to look for time when you're in this school where academics matter a lot. Second is fatigue since we are tired every day from our academics. Then you have to find that motivation somewhere or discipline that you need to get up and you need to do something. You need to accomplish your task.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“Unang-una sa time kasi as a student marami rin namang school activities tapos din mga extra curricular tapos mga personal na ginagawa ko. So, mahirap ipagkasiya lahat ng ‘yon... knowing na limited lang ang time ko.”</p>	<p>Scheduling Conflicts</p>	

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<p><i>“Yes. First is time, because as a student there are many school activities, extracurriculars, and personal things I do. It’s hard to fit everything in, knowing that my time is limited.”</i> – Participant 3</p>		
<p>“Tapos andyan din yung paghanap mo ng customers kasi nga syempre wala ka masyadong oras parang ‘di ka.. kasi dito sa school, as a mahiyain person mahirap kumuha ng costumers na bibili ng product mo kasi nahihiya ako tapos wala rin ako masyadong kilala sa ibang section. So, ‘pag minsan talaga matumal. Tapos sa labas naman ng school like ‘di ka naman kasi makikilala ng ibang tao if ‘di ka magpopost sa social media or ‘di mo iieeganyo yung product mo. So kung limited lang ang time ko, parang limited lang din ang costumers ko.”</p> <p><i>“Then there’s finding customers. Since I don’t have much time and here in school as a shy person, it’s hard to get customers to buy my product because I’m shy and I don’t know many people from other sections. So sometimes sales are slow. Outside of school, people won’t know you unless you post on social media or promote your product. If my time is limited, my customers are also limited.”</i> – Participant 3</p>	<p>Publicity and Marketing Difficulty</p>	

Thematic Chart G centers around the superordinate theme ***Operational Challenges and Competence Development***, specifically focusing on operational challenges. The data provided indicates that respondents encountered several practical difficulties while managing their entrepreneurial activities alongside their academic responsibilities. For instance, Participant 2 described being a “one-man army” with

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regards to managing production, sales, and finances alone. Moreover, other participants reported that financial constraints disrupt production while academic responsibilities result in conflicting schedules. Some participants also noted difficulties in marketing and reaching customers slowed their sales and stunted their potential income. Collectively, the responses reveal that student entrepreneurs must traverse through several operational barriers that influence how they manage, produce, and promote their businesses.

The superordinate theme, *Operational Challenges and Competence Development*, manifested through four subordinate themes such as *production struggles*, *customer expectation pressure*, *scheduling conflicts*, and *publicity and marketing difficulty*. These subordinate themes collectively illustrate the different operational aspects of running a small business that respondents found challenging, particularly within the context of balancing academic obligations with entrepreneurial responsibilities.

The first subordinate theme, *production struggles*, highlights limitations in manpower, resources, and production capacity. Participants described managing all aspects of the business alone, and insufficient profit sometimes prevented them from purchasing materials for additional products. These challenges directly affected the quantity of products available for sale and the ability to meet customer demand. This aligns with Henderson et al. (2024), who noted that resource constraints and limited capital were common obstacles for student entrepreneurs, often restricting production capacity and overall business growth.

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The second subordinate theme, *customer expectation pressure*, reflects the responsibility respondents felt to ensure that their products met acceptable standards of quality and safety. Participants emphasized that producing goods that could harm customers or generate negative feedback would damage their credibility and reputation. This is in line with Salsabillah et al. (2024), who argued that product reliability and perceived quality significantly influence customer satisfaction and loyalty, particularly for small-scale or emerging businesses.

The third subordinate theme, *scheduling conflicts*, explores how academic responsibilities interfered with business management. Participants reported difficulty allocating time for business activities due to school workload, extracurricular commitments, and fatigue. This often led to delayed production or limited business operations, which could affect sales and customer engagement. This corresponds with the findings of Al-Fattal (2025), who highlighted that student entrepreneurs frequently faced time management challenges, balancing academic and entrepreneurial duties, which directly impacts both productivity and personal well-being.

The fourth subordinate theme, *publicity and marketing difficulty*, highlights challenges in promoting products and reaching potential customers. Participants explained that being shy, having limited social connections, and insufficient time for promotion restricted their customer base and slowed sales. This is consistent with Al-Fattal (2024), who identifies marketing limitations and difficulty in customer acquisition as significant barriers for small or student-led businesses.

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Table 8

Annotated Responses to Research Question 3, Interview Question 2

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	In a way, it does because I get stressed sometimes since sometimes, I prioritize my commissions more than my own projects. So, my submissions to projects become late but at the same time, it doesn't affect my academic performance in quizzes and participation in class because it doesn't affect my drawing or writing in the context of what I'm learning. So, for me, it doesn't affect me other than the projects that I'm doing with the commissions and the products that I'm making.	While answering, the participant was relaxed until it came to serious questions.
Participant 2	Okay. So, for example, the time I have to choose between making my products or academics. But most of the time, I choose academics first since that's for the long term. But if there comes a point where I need to let go of entrepreneurship since that's recently what's happening since we are incredibly busy right now. So, I can't really sell something but it is a good side hustle or side goal. And these challenges help me in academics in a positive way as well. Since if you're given so much all at once, you need to develop the time management skills to actually deal with it. And if you develop these skills through balancing entrepreneurship and academic life, then it will be easier to balance your academic life solely if you focus on it.	The participant's answer was well-thought out and was delivered intelligently.
Participant 3	'Pag minsan, for example, Sundays kasi usually kaming nagc-church 'pag Sunday. So, 'pag sobrang busy talaga, naghahalo-halo, nagsasabay-sabay lahat—hindi na ako nakakasama. So, naa-apektuhan din ang quality time tapos minsan din sa kunwari sa pagsabay ng pagkain... 'di na rin, mayroon ding times	The participant shared a sincere response with a reflective tone.

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	<p>na ‘di na rin ako nakakasabay kasi may need akong tapusin puwede [dahil] sa business or school works ko.</p> <p><i>“Sometimes. For example, we usually go to church on Sundays. If I’m really busy and everything overlaps, I don’t get to join them. It affects our quality time. Sometimes during meals, there are times when I can’t eat with them [my family] because I need to finish something for my business or schoolwork.”</i></p>	
Participant 4	<p>These challenges actually does not affect my daily life outside of entrepreneurship. In academic context, it does affect slightly because sometimes as I said earlier, I can't contribute or I can't finish specific activities because I try to sell my products out. That's why.</p>	<p>The participant gave a straightforward answer that was clearly expressed.</p>
Participant 5	<p>I don't think it affects me, especially in academics. No, not really.</p>	<p>The participant provided a brief response that was delivered confidently.</p>

Table 8 shows the responses of the participants regarding the interview question: *Do these challenges affect your daily life outside of entrepreneurship, for instance, in an academic context?* The responses revealed that participants experienced varying degrees of influence on their academic performance, time management, and personal routines as a result of balancing their businesses with school responsibilities. While some participants reported minimal or no academic impact, others indicated occasional delays in submissions, reduced participation in class activities, and the need to prioritize tasks

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carefully. The participants’ responses also reflected differing approaches to managing their dual roles, ranging from conscious prioritization of academics to development of adaptive time management strategies. Emotional responses varied from relaxed reflection to mild stress when recalling the effect of entrepreneurship on their daily lives.

Participant 1 expressed that while prioritizing commissions sometimes caused delays in project submissions, their academic performance remained largely unaffected. Participant 2 emphasized the importance of prioritizing academics over entrepreneurship for long-term goals, noting that handling multiple responsibilities improved their time management skills. Participant 3 reported that business tasks occasionally interfered with family time and personal routines, such as missing meals or church activities. Participant 4 acknowledged slight disruptions to academic participation due to the demands of selling products, while Participant 5 indicated that entrepreneurship had minimal effect on their academic life. Overall, the participants demonstrated awareness of the challenges of balancing entrepreneurship and academics, as well as strategies to manage these competing demands.

Thematic Chart H

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
“Most of the time, I choose academics first since that's for the long term.” – <i>Participant 2</i>	Prioritization of Academics	Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management

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<p>“Sometimes I prioritize my commissions more than my own projects. So, my submissions to projects become late.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“Sometimes I can’t finish specific activities because I try to sell my products out.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>	<p>Academic Workload Impact</p>	
<p>“It doesn’t affect my academic performance in quizzes and participation in class because it doesn’t affect my drawing or writing in the context of what I’m learning.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“I don’t think it affects me, especially in academics. No, not really.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Perceived Academic Influence</p>	
<p>“These challenges help me in academics in a positive way as well... it will be easier to balance your academic life solely if you focus on it.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p>	<p>Adaptive Coping Strategies</p>	

Thematic Chart H centers around the superordinate theme ***Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management***, specifically under balancing multiple responsibilities amid academic and entrepreneurial demands. Participants reported that they often prioritized their academic responsibilities over business activities, recognizing the long-term importance of school. At the same time, some noted that completing business tasks, such as fulfilling product orders, occasionally caused them to delay academic assignments. These experiences illustrate that student entrepreneurs must

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constantly make decisions about how to allocate their time and energy, balancing immediate business obligations with ongoing academic requirements.

The superordinate theme *Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management* emerged through four subordinate themes, which are prioritization of academics, academic workload impact, perceived academic influence, and adaptive coping strategies. Overall, these themes illustrate how respondents managed the demands of their education while simultaneously running their businesses, highlighting the strategies and trade-offs they employed to maintain both academic performance and entrepreneurial activities.

The first subordinate theme, *prioritization of academics*, highlights how respondents often viewed academic performance as a long-term priority, consciously making choices that favored school over entrepreneurial tasks. This aligns with findings by Liu et al. (2024), who argue that student entrepreneurs tend to prioritize formal education due to its perceived long-term value.

The second subordinate theme, *academic workload impact*, explains how business activities sometimes interfered with the completion of school tasks. Some respondents reported being unable to finish academic responsibilities because they were focused on entrepreneurial work, while others believed that entrepreneurship did not negatively affect their academic performance in tests or class participation. These mixed perceptions correspond with recent studies showing that entrepreneurial involvement can have both positive and neutral effects on academic performance, depending on time

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management skills and the nature of tasks being balanced (Agbayani & Paglinawan, 2025).

The third subordinate theme, *perceived academic influence*, illustrates that respondents recognized both potential sacrifices and benefits. For some, entrepreneurship was described as a good “side hustle” that could be let go if necessary, indicating a contingent commitment to business activities based on academic demands. Others noted that responsibilities sometimes affected personal routines, such as missing meals with family. These experiences align with research suggesting that student entrepreneurs often navigate complex personal and academic trade-offs, balancing identity, priorities, and social commitments while pursuing business goals (Manzi-Puertas et al., 2024).

The fourth subordinate theme, *adaptive coping strategies*, reflects how participants viewed their challenges as opportunities for personal growth and skill development. Some expressed that these experiences helped them understand the importance of focus and prioritization, not only for academics but for future responsibilities. This is consistent with findings by Valencia-Arias et al. (2025), who identified that student entrepreneurs often develop resilience, time-management skills, and strategic decision-making as coping mechanisms when balancing multiple roles.

Table 9

Annotated Responses to Research Question 3, Interview Question 3

Participants	Responses	Researcher's
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		Observation
Participant 1	<p>For that, as I've said, my challenges are in picking up commissions. A way for me to handle those challenges is communication with the customer. Wherein, what the customer is doing is just picking up the product that I'm selling or the commission to the gate of SciTech so that it doesn't interfere with my schedule and also doesn't interfere with his schedule. Or even sometimes, just finding a new product to sell or to make money off that won't be harmful to the teacher's opinion so that it will be respectful to them.</p>	<p>The participant reflected on ways to handle challenges.</p>
Participant 2	<p>Okay. So, most of the challenges I was able to handle since I know someone that has started the entrepreneurship in school. And I have gotten advice from them on how I am supposed to interact with people, how I'm supposed to open a product or introduce a product, and how I am supposed to produce and sell it. Yes. So, for the most part since generally the more problems you have and the more you fix them, the more you learn from your mistakes and the more you become more grown in handling real life challenges. So, let's say in my academic life again, in fatigue or the fatigue hindrance part in entrepreneurship. If you can motivate yourself to keep working even though you are tired, then it will be easy for you to remove procrastination as well. Since I was able to do this when I'm tired. So, it should be easy when I'm not tired and I'm just procrastinating. So, it also lessens that part of me and it has made me into a more productive person than I was before.</p>	<p>The participant was enthusiastic while answering the question.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Unang-una, 'di ko naman siya magagawa without the support of my parents. Sila talaga yung unang nandyan to support me noong nagsisimula pa lang ako. Tapos hanggang sa lumaki nang lumaki. Ayon, with the help of my parents and friends tapos yung mga challenges naman na 'yon, I use it to become stronger din kasi 'di naman mawawala yung challenges na 'yon lalo na't entrepreneurship ang</p>	<p>The participant was eager to share their experience.</p>

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	<p>pinasok mo. So, marami talagang challenges and solusyon doon is matuto sa experience.</p> <p><i>“First of all, I couldn’t have done it without my parents’ support. They were there to support me when I was just starting. With the help of my parents and friends, I handled the challenges. I use those challenges to become stronger because challenges won’t disappear, especially in entrepreneurship. The solution is to learn from experience.”</i></p>	
Participant 4	<p>I was able to handle the challenges with the help of my parents specifically since they helped me or guided me through entrepreneurship since they have experience. They gave me tips, they gave me plans that can help with my business to spread out more or enlarge deeper and since they helped me a lot in my business specifically, they also helped me financially. They let me borrow money so that I can create a cycle for my profit and yeah. It's hard for me to handle finances at specific times or period when I try to sell my products, especially when there are times that students don't have enough budget or don't have enough money to buy my products.</p>	<p>The participant was cheerful while answering the question.</p>
Participant 5	<p>So, again, I didn't face any challenges, and there wasn't anything that posed a hindrance. So, yeah.</p>	<p>The participant seemed calm while answering the question.</p>

Table 9 shows the responses of the participants regarding the interview question: *How were you able to handle these challenges, and were you able to use these hindrances to your advantage? How so?* The responses revealed that participants adopted different strategies to manage the challenges they encountered in their entrepreneurial activities.

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Several participants emphasized the importance of communication, external guidance, and support systems in overcoming these difficulties. Others indicated that the challenges they experienced became opportunities for personal development, enabling them to improve their productivity, discipline, and problem-solving abilities. The participants' responses also reflected varying ways of coping with these challenges, ranging from adapting business practices and seeking advice to relying on family support and learning from experience. Emotional responses varied from reflective explanations to confident statements when discussing how they managed their entrepreneurial challenges.

Participant 1 explained that they were able to handle their challenges by maintaining communication with customers, particularly by arranging product pickups at the school gate to prevent disruptions to their schedule. Participant 2 shared that they managed their challenges by seeking advice from someone who had prior experience in entrepreneurship within the school, which helped them learn how to introduce products, interact with customers, and manage production and selling. The participant further noted that overcoming fatigue and other difficulties motivated them to become more disciplined and productive, allowing them to reduce procrastination and handle tasks more efficiently. Participant 3 highlighted the support they received from their parents and friends, explaining that these individuals helped them manage the challenges they encountered while also encouraging them to learn from their experiences. Participant 4 similarly credited their parents for guiding them through entrepreneurship by providing advice, business strategies, and financial assistance when necessary. This support enabled

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the participant to manage financial difficulties and maintain the cycle of their business operations. Meanwhile, Participant 5 stated that they did not experience significant challenges in their entrepreneurial activities and therefore did not identify any hindrances to overcome. Overall, the responses demonstrate that student entrepreneurs addressed challenges through communication, guidance from experienced individuals, family support, and personal growth, enabling them to adapt and continue their business activities.

Thematic Chart I

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“A way for me to handle those challenges is communication with the customer... finding a new product to sell... that won’t be harmful to the teacher’s opinion.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p>	<p>Problem-Solving Strategies</p>	<p>Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management</p>
<p>“If you can motivate yourself to keep working even though you are tired, then it will be easy to remove procrastination... it has made me into a more productive person than I was before.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p>	<p>Self-Management and Motivation</p>	
<p>“Unang-una, ‘di ko naman siya magagawa without the support of my parents. Sila talaga yung unang nandyan to support me noong nagsisimula pa lang ako.” <i>“I couldn’t have done it without my parents’ support. They were there to support me when I</i></p>	<p>Parental Support</p>	<p>Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship</p>

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<p><i>was just starting.”</i> – Participant 3</p> <p>“I was able to handle the challenges with the help of my parents... they gave me tips, plans, and even financial support.” – Participant 4</p>		
<p>“Tapos yung mga challenges naman na ‘yon, I use it to become stronger din kasi ‘di naman mawawala yung challenges na ‘yon lalo na't entrepreneurship ang pinasok mo. So, marami talagang challenges and solusyon doon is matuto sa experience.”</p> <p><i>“I use those challenges to become stronger because challenges won't disappear... the solution is to learn from experience.”</i> – Participant 3</p> <p>“I have gotten advice from someone who started entrepreneurship... the more problems you have and the more you fix them, the more you learn from your mistakes.” – Participant 2</p>	<p>Learning from Experience</p>	

Thematic Chart I centers around the superordinate theme ***Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management and Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship***. Specifically, the responses to this particular question centered around coping with entrepreneurial challenges and support systems with learning strategies respectively. Participants reported that they managed obstacles in running their businesses by developing practical and personal strategies. Some explained that they addressed issues by improving communication with customers or adjusting products to

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avoid conflicts, while others focused on self-motivation to maintain productivity despite fatigue or procrastination. These experiences illustrate that student entrepreneurs must constantly develop both practical solutions and personal resilience to navigate challenges effectively.

The superordinate theme, *Academic and Entrepreneurial Role Management*, was identified through two subordinate themes: *problem-solving strategies* and *self-management and motivation*. These themes highlight how respondents handled operational and personal challenges to sustain their business activities.

The first subordinate theme, *problem-solving strategies*, emphasizes the practical approaches participants used to overcome challenges. Respondents described identifying new products, addressing customer concerns, and anticipating potential issues to ensure smooth business operations. This aligns with findings by Manzi-Puertas et al. (2024), who noted that proactive problem-solving was a key strategy student entrepreneurs employ to overcome operational barriers and maintain business continuity.

The second subordinate theme, *self-management and motivation*, reflects the personal effort required to persist despite fatigue or competing responsibilities. Participants shared that motivating themselves to continue working enhanced their productivity and discipline, allowing them to meet both entrepreneurial and academic expectations. This corresponds with research by Valencia-Arias et al. (2025b), which emphasized that resilience and self-regulation were critical for student entrepreneurs to sustain performance and achieve goals.

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Thematic Chart I also centers around the superordinate theme ***Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship***. Participants indicated that external support and lessons learned from experience were vital in overcoming entrepreneurial challenges. Some relied on guidance, encouragement, or financial assistance from their parents, while others emphasized learning from previous mistakes to improve future business decisions. These experiences show that student entrepreneurs depend on both social support and reflective learning to develop competence and confidence.

The superordinate theme, ***Support Systems and Learning Strategies***, was identified through two subordinate themes: ***parental support*** and ***learning from experience***. These themes highlight how respondents drew on relationships and personal reflection to manage challenges effectively.

The first subordinate theme, ***parental support***, demonstrates how participants relied on their parents for advice, encouragement, and practical assistance, particularly during the early stages of their business ventures. This is consistent with studies by Sevilla-Bernardo et al. (2024), which show that social and familial support enhances confidence and performance among student entrepreneurs.

The second subordinate theme, ***learning from experience***, emphasizes how participants viewed challenges as opportunities for growth. Respondents noted that encountering and resolving problems helped them develop skills, apply lessons to future situations, and make better business decisions. Recent research supports this perspective,

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indicating that reflective learning and experiential problem-solving are key factors in building entrepreneurial competence (Alkaabi & Senghore, 2024).

RQ 4. How do perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and social influences shape entrepreneurial intention among SRSTHS students?

This question explores how perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and social influences affect the respondents' entrepreneurial intention. It provides insights regarding the circumstances that affected their decision to become a student entrepreneur.

Table 10

Annotated Responses to Research Question 4, Interview Question 1

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	For me, the only appeal of entrepreneurship is the money that I would be able to make. And also because it would also allow me to improve my skills in writing and also drawing and sometimes even in music making. Sometimes, I would get commissions like making a song or even just writing a [sic] lyrics. So, it really did help me in developing those skills. That's why it was appealing to me because not only does it produce money, does [sic] it only make [sic] my efforts and works seem valuable, it also helps me with improving my skills.	The participant answered calmly and confidently.
Participant 2	Money and freedom. So, if you have money, you have freedom. Freedom to choose what you want to do. Freedom to buy what you want. And entrepreneurship is the most direct way to gain freedom and money.	The participant appeared to enjoy responding to

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	And it affected my decision to pursue my own business because I saw that there's a market here in SRSTHS that I can capitalize on.	this question.
Participant 3	<p>What motivates me is yung thought na may sarili akong pera. Like I don't have to ask my parents... Yeah, for money like syempre mga wants ko I can buy it on my own like from the money from my business.</p> <p><i>“What motivates me is the thought that I have my own money. I don't have to ask my parents. Yes, for money. For example, my wants, I can buy them on my own using the money from my business.”</i></p>	The participant answered with greater conviction in this question.
Participant 4	<p>What made entrepreneurship appealing to me is that I saw my parents hardworking, their diligence to provide proper care to us made me pursue my dreams to become a student entrepreneur. Especially since I want to help them financially since I don't want to see them financially unstable so as much as possible, me myself, I try to help them accomplish those stuff. These decisions actually helped me pursue my own business since they also helped me pursue it because they are there to support me since I was there to support them too.</p>	The participant showed great appreciation toward his/her parents while answering.
Participant 5	<p>I guess the factor that really made entrepreneurship appealing for me is that, of course, I earned money. Or like, kidding aside, I also wanted to learn how to budget when buying materials and also how to properly price my products so that somehow it's affordable to others, but still, I earn money from it.</p>	The participant responded with humor and enjoyed answering the question.

Table 10 presents the responses of the participants to the question: *What made entrepreneurship appealing to you and how did that affect your decision to pursue your own business?* The responses of the participants seemed to coincide in their viewpoints regarding money. To them, a major contributor to the appeal of entrepreneurship is the

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ability to attain a sense of financial freedom. According to Participant 1, “If you have money, you have freedom. Freedom to choose what you want to do. Freedom to buy what you want. And entrepreneurship is the most direct way to gain freedom and money.”

Participants 2, 3, and 5 echo this sentiment, each stating that entrepreneurship helps fund their wants and needs without needing to ask for money from their parents.

Participant 4, on the other hand, while generally agreeing with the views of the other 4 participants, also perceived parental return-of-service as another major appeal of entrepreneurship. According to them, “What made entrepreneurship appealing to me is that I saw my parents hardworking, their diligence to provide proper care to us made me pursue my dreams to become a student entrepreneur.” This shows that household perceptions influence entrepreneurial aspirations to some degree.

All participants exhibited some degree of confidence of lightheartedness while answering the question.

Thematic Chart J

Participants’ Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
“What made entrepreneurship appealing to me is that I saw my parents hardworking, their diligence to provide proper care to us made me pursue my dreams to become a student entrepreneur. Especially since I want to help them financially since I don't want to see them financially unstable so as much as possible, me myself, I try to help them accomplish those	Family Encouragement	Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship
	Household Financial Contribution	

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<p>stuff. These decisions actually helped me pursue my own business since they also helped me pursue it because they are there to support me since I was there to support them too.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>		
<p>“Money and freedom. So, if you have money, you have freedom. Freedom to choose what you want to do. Freedom to buy what you want. And entrepreneurship is the most direct way to gain freedom and money. And it affected my decision to pursue my own business because I saw that there's a market here in SRSTHS that I can capitalize on.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“What motivates me is yung thought na may sarili akong pera. Like I don't have to ask my parents... Yeah, for money like syempre mga wants ko I can buy it on my own like from the money from my business.”</p> <p><i>“What motivates me is the thought that I have my own money. I don't have to ask my parents. Yes, for money. For example, my wants, I can buy them on my own using the money from my business.”</i> – <i>Participant 3</i></p> <p>“I guess the factor that really made entrepreneurship appealing for me is that, of course, I earned money. ..., but still, I earn money from it.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Aspirations of Financial Independence</p>	<p>Financial Empowerment and Autonomy</p>
<p>“For me, the only appeal of entrepreneurship is the money that I would be able to make. ... That's why it was appealing to me because not only does it produce money, does it only make my efforts and works seem valuable.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p>	<p>Budgeting and Financial Literacy</p>	

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<p>“...Or like, kidding aside, I also wanted to learn how to budget when buying materials and also how to properly price my products so that somehow it's affordable to others, but still, I earn money from it.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>		
<p>“For me, the only appeal of entrepreneurship is the money that I would be able to make. And also because it would also allow me to improve my skills in writing and also drawing and sometimes even in music making. Sometimes, I would get commissions like making a song or even just writing a lyrics. So, it really did help me in developing those skills. That's why it was appealing to me because not only does it produce money, does it only make my efforts and works seem valuable, it also helps me with improving my skills.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p>	<p>Technical Skill Development</p>	<p>Capacity Building</p>

The thematic analysis of Table 20 revealed three primary superordinate themes:

Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship, Financial Empowerment and Autonomy, and Capacity Building. Within these superordinate themes, several subordinate themes emerged that provide deeper insight into the participants' entrepreneurial motivations.

Under ***Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship***, the subordinate theme of ***family encouragement*** captures how parental modeling and support shaped participants' entrepreneurial aspirations. Participant 4 explicitly articulated this influence, stating that witnessing their parents' “diligence to provide proper care to us

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made me pursue my dreams to become a student entrepreneur.” This finding suggests that parental work ethic serves as a powerful observational model for students, normalizing entrepreneurial behavior as a viable and respectable pursuit.

The second subordinate theme, *household financial contribution*, reflects a more reciprocal dynamic, wherein participants viewed entrepreneurship as a means of supporting their families rather than merely funding personal expenses. Participant 4's desire to "help them financially since I don't want to see them financially unstable" indicates that for some students, entrepreneurship functions as a mechanism for intergenerational support and familial solidarity, extending beyond individual benefit to encompass collective household welfare.

Within the superordinate theme of *Financial Empowerment and Autonomy*, two subordinate themes were identified: *aspirations of financial independence and budgeting and financial literacy*. The subordinate theme of *aspirations of financial independence* captures the psychological and practical freedom that participants associated with earning their own money. Participant 2's assertion that “if you have money, you have freedom—freedom to choose what you want to do, freedom to buy what you want” encapsulates this sentiment, while Participant 3 emphasized the independence gained from “not having to ask my parents” for money. This autonomy extends beyond mere purchasing power to encompass a sense of self-determination and reduced dependency on family allowances.

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The subordinate theme of *budgeting and financial literacy* reveals the educational dimension of entrepreneurial engagement. Participant 5 explicitly articulated this learning objective, stating their desire to learn “how to budget when buying materials and also how to properly price my products.” This finding indicates that participants view entrepreneurship not only as an income-generating activity but as a practical context for developing essential financial management competencies that extend beyond the immediate business context.

Lastly, the superordinate theme of *Capacity Building* contained the subordinate theme of *technical skill development*. Participant 1 described how their commission-based business model created opportunities to “improve skills in writing, drawing, and music making.” This finding suggests that entrepreneurship provides a structured framework for skill validation and refinement, wherein student entrepreneurs receive tangible feedback—both financial and social—on their creative and technical outputs. As Participant 1 observed, engaging in commissions makes their “efforts and works seem valuable,” indicating that entrepreneurship serves as a bridge between creative expression and professional competency development, validating students' abilities through market response.

Table 11

Annotated Responses to Research Question 4, Interview Question 2

Participants	Responses	Researcher's
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		Observation
Participant 1	Since entrepreneurship is accessible to everyone, especially students and sometimes even teachers, it also depends on what they want to do. That really affected me in making a decision that I will be an entrepreneur in a way that is accessible to me, in a way that I can provide my skills to them, in a way that I use my skills to provide the products and the commissions that they ask me to do. So, for me to have a budget and price for my products and also to help the customers in their needs.	The participant answered in an in-depth manner, as if eager to give advice.
Participant 2	I thought that entrepreneurship was very achievable since you see a lot of people doing it. And as a student, it's even more achievable since you have a lot of peers and a lot of potential customers around you.	The participant answered with sheer confidence.
Participant 3	Achievable naman siya basta mayroon kang motivation to start and you're willing to take risks. And mayroon kang puhunan, syempre 'di mawawala diyan yung paglabas mo ng pera. So, dapat matanggap mo na yung puhunan mo either 'di mababalik or like malulugi ka. Kasi ang entrepreneurship 'di naman 'yan puro kita nang kita. So, dapat mayroon kang determination tsaka perseverance. Oo, para hindi ka mawalan ng lakas ng loob para ituloy. Kasi may mga challenges na maf-face mo during your entrepreneurship time 'di naman 'yon mawawala. <i>"It's achievable as long as you have the motivation to start and you're willing to take risks. And you need capital. Of course, you have to spend money. You have to accept that your capital might not return or that you might lose money. Entrepreneurship isn't all profit. You need determination and perseverance so you won't lose courage to continue. There will always be challenges during your entrepreneurship journey."</i>	The participant's answer was well-thought out and was delivered intelligently.
Participant 4	In my perspective, entrepreneurship is achievable and it really affected my decision on pursuing on to	The participant seemed to

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	becoming an entrepreneur since [<i>sic</i>] ever since I was a kid, I always help my parents sell fruits in our fruit stall, sell packs of nuts especially. I am very proud of what my parents have become and that made me pursue my dreams to become an entrepreneur and I really think it is achievable with the right guidance from my parents especially since they have experience on becoming entrepreneurs.	reminisce about their past experiences in a positive manner.
Participant 5	When I saw my batch mates selling their own products, and they looked successful, I thought. Oh, maybe I can do the same.	The participant responded concisely.

Table 11 presents the responses of the participants to the interview question: *How did your perception of how achievable entrepreneurship was affect your decision to become an entrepreneur?* This question produced responses which, though positive, were sentimentally diverse. For instance, Participant 1 expressed a feeling of relief whenever she performs services for fellow students and teachers. According to her, “That really affected me in making a decision that I will be an entrepreneur in a way that is accessible to me, in a way that I can provide my skills to them, in a way that I use my skills to provide the products and the commissions that they ask me to do.” This shows that, for some, entrepreneurship provides satisfaction and a sense of fulfillment which lets them pursue it even more.

Supplementarily, Participants 2 and 5 expressed curiosity observing their co-entrepreneur batchmates. They perceived entrepreneurship as easy to achieve, mainly due to the fact that their peers seemed successful selling their products. This observation encouraged them to gauge the feasibility of pursuing their own entrepreneurial ventures.

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From the words of Participant 2, “I thought that entrepreneurship was very achievable since you see a lot of people doing it.” Participant 5 added onto this idea by saying, “When I saw my batch mates selling their own products, and they looked successful, I thought, Oh, maybe I can do the same.”

Participant 3 viewed the situation at a different angle. To them, risk-taking is a big part of pursuing entrepreneurship. They perceived entrepreneurship as being multifaceted, requiring careful consideration of multiple factors before engagement. “It’s achievable as long as you have the motivation to start and you’re willing to take risks. And you need capital. Of course, you have to spend money. You have to accept that your capital might not return or that you might lose money.”

Lastly, Participant 4 sees parental guidance as a core factor in making entrepreneurial decisions. The participant views parents as authoritative figures which they perceive can point budding entrepreneurs in the right direction. Additionally, during the interview, the participant reflected on their childhood experiences of assisting with their parents’ entrepreneurial ventures.

Thematic Chart K

Participants’ Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
“Since entrepreneurship is accessible to everyone, especially students and sometimes even teachers, it also depends on what they want to do. That really affected me in making a	Market Position Awareness	Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations

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<p>decision that I will be an entrepreneur in a way that is accessible to me, in a way that I can provide my skills to them, in a way that I use my skills to provide the products and the commissions that they ask me to do. So, for me to have a budget and price for my products and also to help the customers in their needs.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“And as a student, it's even more achievable since you have a lot of peers and a lot of potential customers around you.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“Achievable naman siya basta mayroon kang motivation to start and you're willing to take risks...”</p> <p><i>“It’s achievable as long as you have the motivation to start and you’re willing to take risks...”</i> – <i>Participant 3</i></p>		
<p>“I thought that entrepreneurship was very achievable since you see a lot of people doing it. And as a student, it's even more achievable since you have a lot of peers and a lot of potential customers around you.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“When I saw my batch mates selling their own products, and they looked successful, I thought, Oh, maybe I can do the same.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Peer Creativity Influence</p> <hr/> <p>Entrepreneurial Curiosity</p>	<p>Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship</p>
<p>“Achievable naman siya basta mayroon kang motivation to start and you're willing to take risks. And mayroon kang puhunan, syempre ‘di mawawala diyan yung paglabas mo ng pera. So, dapat matanggap mo na yung puhunan mo either ‘di mababalik or like malulugi ka. Kasi</p>	<p>Production Efficiency Struggles</p> <hr/> <p>Risk Assessment</p>	

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<p>ang entrepreneurship ‘di naman ‘yan puro kita nang kita. So, dapat mayroon kang determination tsaka perseverance. Oo, para hindi ka mawalan ng lakas ng loob para ituloy. Kasi may mga challenges na maf-face mo during your entrepreneurship time ‘di naman ‘yon mawawala.”</p> <p><i>“It’s achievable as long as you have the motivation to start and you’re willing to take risks. And you need capital. Of course you have to spend money. You have to accept that your capital might not return or that you might lose money. Entrepreneurship isn’t all profit. You need determination and perseverance so you won’t lose courage to continue. There will always be challenges during your entrepreneurship journey.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p>		
<p>“In my perspective, entrepreneurship is achievable and it really affected my decision on pursuing on to becoming an entrepreneur since ever since I was a kid, I always help my parents sell fruits in our fruit stall, sell packs of nuts especially. I am very proud of what my parents have become and that made me pursue my dreams to become an entrepreneur and I really think it is achievable with the right guidance from my parents especially since they have experience on becoming entrepreneurs.”</p> <p>– Participant 4</p>	<p>Family Encouragement</p>	
	<p>Entrepreneurial Excitement</p>	

Thematic Chart K underscores the thematic analysis of participants' perceptions regarding the achievability of entrepreneurship. The analysis revealed two superordinate themes: *Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations* and *Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship*, each encompassing distinct

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subordinate themes that illuminate how students assess and act upon entrepreneurial opportunities.

Within the superordinate theme of *Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations*, two subordinate themes were identified: *market position awareness* and *risk assessment*. The subordinate theme of *market position awareness* reflects participants' understanding of how to position themselves within the school marketplace. Participant 1 demonstrated sophisticated market orientation by recognizing that entrepreneurship is “accessible to everyone, especially students,” and strategically positioning their skill-based offerings to meet customer needs. This awareness extends to understanding the immediate advantages of the school environment, as Participant 2 noted that "as a student, it's even more achievable since you have a lot of peers and a lot of potential customers around you."

The second subordinate theme, *risk assessment*, captures the more cautionary perspective articulated by Participant 3, who emphasized that entrepreneurship requires willingness to “take risks” and acceptance that “capital might not return.” This risk awareness, coupled with the recognition that “entrepreneurship isn't all profit,” demonstrates a mature understanding of business uncertainty that distinguishes these participants from novice entrepreneurs who might underestimate potential losses. Participant 3's emphasis on needing “determination and perseverance so you won't lose courage to continue” further illustrates how risk assessment informs the psychological preparedness required for entrepreneurial persistence.

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The superordinate theme of *Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship* encompassed two subordinate themes: *peer creativity influence* and *entrepreneurial curiosity*. The subordinate theme of *peer creativity influence* emerged from participants who cited observation of successful peers as a catalyst for their own entrepreneurial pursuits. Participant 2 noted that entrepreneurship appeared “very achievable since you see a lot of people doing it,” while Participant 5 shared that witnessing batch mates who “looked successful” prompted the realization that “maybe I can do the same.” This social learning process, wherein students observe and model peer behavior, aligns with social cognitive theory and demonstrates how vicarious experience shapes entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

The subordinate theme of *entrepreneurial curiosity* captures the cognitive engagement that transforms observation into action. Participants did not merely passively observe peers but actively considered the implications for their own capabilities, engaging in what might be termed entrepreneurial imagination—the cognitive process of projecting oneself into the role of entrepreneur based on observed peer success.

Table 12

Annotated Responses to Research Question 4, Interview Question 3

Participants	Responses	Researcher’s Observation
Participant 1	The social factors that I really did take note before becoming an entrepreneur is [sic] the [figures of	The participant exhibited a

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	<p>authority], ... as I've said, I did look into the rule books and also some of the laws in our countries [<i>sic</i>] ... and I did not see that much evidence to prove that it was not allowed. So, I did take note of the evidences and the factual literacy that I did see in the library to make the decision that I will continue to be an entrepreneur even if some [figure of authority] says that it's not allowed.</p> <p><i>Note. Identifying information has been abstracted to protect participant confidentiality.</i></p>	<p>high level of agency and defiance. They exhibited an analytical tone.</p>
Participant 2	<p>My parents are not entrepreneurs. But they are very supportive of me being an entrepreneur. My friends, on the other hand, some of them are entrepreneurs too. And they give me advice and they also buy from me. So, the social factors around me are very positive.</p>	<p>The participant maintained a relaxed and cheerful demeanor.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Yung immediate family ko, hindi sila inclined sa business. Pero yung other brothers ko mayroon silang business. I'm thinking about parang nakuha ko siya sa brother ko—middle child na brother kasi siya yung pinaka-una sa family namin magbusiness. So, noong nahanap ko yung gusto ko. Ang first business ko is about sa dogs. Why not i-share ko naman sa iba? Kasi parang win-win situation. Nakikinabang ako, mga dogs ko, kikita rin naman ako. Wala namang lost. So, hanggang sa nagtuloy tuloy na nagtry din naman ako ng ibang binebenta. For example, dito sa school nagbebenta ako ng mga binabake ko or mga food na nirere-sell ko.</p> <p><i>“My immediate family isn't inclined toward business, but my other siblings have businesses. I think I got it from my middle brother because he was the first in our family to start a business. My first business was about dogs. I thought, why not share it with others? It's a win-win situation. I benefit, my dogs benefit, and I earn. There's no loss. So it continued, and I also tried selling other things. For example, here in school I sell baked goods or food that I resell.”</i></p>	<p>The participant appeared inspired when discussing their older brother, nodding frequently as if recalling specific memories.</p>

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Participant 4	My friends and my family actually encouraged me to continue my business. They were there with me since the time I pursued my passion, or the time I decided, or the time that I shared my ideas on becoming a student entrepreneur. They were helping me financially and emotionally. They actually helped me multiple times. They helped me through buying products and materials. They were there to spend time with me while I was involved with my business.	The participant was cheerful as they reflected on their experiences.
Participant 5	I guess, again, a social factor that affected my decision in becoming an entrepreneur were the reactions of my classmates buying from other entrepreneurs in our section. I also noticed that our teachers are very supportive of what we are selling. I also noticed that teachers are super supportive teachers in selling baked goods, cookies, and stuff. They would even... So I guess that really affected my decision in wanting to do the same and start selling my own goods.	The participant's gaze was focused and steady as they described the 'reactions' of classmates. They seemed to be recounting a mental tally of successful transactions they had witnessed.

Table 12 presents responses to the interview question: *How did different social factors affect your decision to become an entrepreneur?* This question produced conflicting responses, particularly from Participants 1 and 5. Participant 1 shared her experiences with the inconsistencies of school rules affecting her business operations, and general friction with certain figures of authority. Meanwhile, Participant 5 echoed the opposite idea: that her business garnered utmost support from the teachers. The rest of the

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participants, however, agreed on one factor: parental support and guidance. Overall, the participants displayed mixed emotions while answering the question.

Thematic Chart L

Participants' Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“The social factors that I really did take note before becoming an entrepreneur is the [figures of authority], ... as I've said, I did look into the rule books and also some of the laws in our countries ... and I did not see that much evidence to prove that it was not allowed. So, I did take note of the evidences and the factual literacy that I did see in the library to make the decision that I will continue to be an entrepreneur even if some [figure of authority] says that it's not allowed.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p>	Regulatory Friction	Institutional Constraints and Adaptation
	Perceived Policy Indeterminacy	
<p>“My parents are not entrepreneurs. But they are very supportive of me being an entrepreneur. My friends, on the other hand, some of them are entrepreneurs too. And they give me advice and they also buy from me. So, the social factors around me are very positive.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>"Yung immediate family ko, hindi sila inclined sa business. Pero yung other brothers ko mayroon silang business. I'm thinking about parang nakuha ko siya sa brother ko—middle child na brother kasi siya yung pinaka-una sa family namin magbusiness. So, noong nahanap ko yung gusto ko. Ang first business ko is about sa dogs. Why not i-share ko naman sa iba? Kasi parang win-win situation.</p>	Parental Support	Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship
	Peer Entrepreneurial Networks	
	Teacher Patronage	

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<p>Nakikinabang ako, mga dogs ko, kikita rin naman ako. Wala namang lost. So, hanggang sa nagtuloy tuloy na nagtry din naman ako ng ibang binebenta. For example, dito sa school nagbebenta ako ng mga binabake ko or mga food na nirere-sell ko.”</p> <p><i>“My immediate family isn’t inclined toward business, but my other siblings have businesses. I think I got it from my middle brother because he was the first in our family to start a business. My first business was about dogs. I thought, why not share it with others? It’s a win-win situation. I benefit, my dogs benefit, and I earn. There’s no loss. So it continued, and I also tried selling other things. For example, here in school I sell baked goods or food that I resell.”</i></p> <p>– Participant 3</p> <p>“My friends and my family actually encouraged me to continue my business. They were there with me since the time I pursued my passion, or the time I decided, or the time that I shared my ideas on becoming a student entrepreneur. They were helping me financially and emotionally. They actually helped me multiple times. They helped me through buying products and materials. They were there to spend time with me while I was involved with my business.”</p> <p>– Participant 4</p> <p>“I guess, again, a social factor that affected my decision in becoming an entrepreneur were the reactions of my classmates buying from other entrepreneurs in our section. I also noticed that our teachers are very supportive of what we are selling. I also noticed that teachers are super supportive teachers in selling baked goods, cookies, and stuff. They would even... So I</p>		
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guess that really affected my decision in wanting to do the same and start selling my own goods.” – Participant 5		
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The thematic analysis of Thematic Chart L identified two superordinate themes: ***Institutional Constraints and Adaptation*** and ***Supportive Social Environment for Entrepreneurship***. Within these superordinate themes, several subordinate themes emerged that illuminate the complex social landscape student entrepreneurs must navigate.

Under the superordinate theme of ***Institutional Constraints and Adaptation***, the subordinate theme of ***regulatory friction*** captures participants’ experiences with ambiguous or inconsistently enforced school policies. Participant 1 described conducting independent research into school rule books and DepEd regulations to verify whether their business activities were actually prohibited, noting they “did look into the rule books and also some of the laws” to find “evidence to prove that it was not allowed.” This proactive approach to policy interpretation reflects what might be termed regulatory literacy—the ability to navigate institutional rules and identify discrepancies between stated policy and enforcement practice.

The subordinate theme of ***perceived policy indeterminacy*** emerged from the participant's observation that despite finding “no true rules” prohibiting their business activities, they continued to encounter resistance from authority figures who “say that it's prohibited.” This gap between written policy and lived experience creates what

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participants perceive as arbitrary enforcement, forcing them to develop adaptive strategies including operating discreetly to maintain their entrepreneurial activities while avoiding institutional sanction.

The superordinate theme of *Social and Motivational Determinants of Entrepreneurship* encompassed three subordinate themes: *parental support*, *peer entrepreneurial networks*, and *teacher patronage*. The subordinate theme of *parental support* emerged consistently across participants, with Participant 2 noting that while their “parents are not entrepreneurs,” they remain “very supportive” of their entrepreneurial pursuits. Participant 3 credited their “middle brother” as the first family member to start a business, suggesting that entrepreneurial behavior can propagate through sibling modeling and influence.

The subordinate theme of *peer entrepreneurial networks* captured the practical support entrepreneurs receive from fellow student business owners. Participant 2 described how entrepreneur friends provide both “advice” and customer patronage, creating a mutually supportive ecosystem within the school.

The subordinate theme of *teacher patronage* emerged from Participant 5's observation that teachers are “super supportive of what we are selling,” noting that teacher encouragement and purchasing behavior “really affected my decision in wanting to do the same.” This finding indicates that teacher support extends beyond verbal encouragement to include direct customer participation, validating student entrepreneurial efforts through tangible economic engagement.

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Collectively, these subordinate themes reveal that student entrepreneurs operate within a complex social ecology comprising supportive elements (parents, peers, teachers) and constraining elements (institutional policies, authority figure resistance). Their ability to navigate this landscape, leveraging supports while adapting to constraints, demonstrates sophisticated social and institutional competence developed through entrepreneurial engagement.

RQ 5. What are the ethical considerations taken into account by the student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?

This question examines how ethical considerations affect the decisions made by the respondents' in their entrepreneurship. It presents an overview on how these considerations influenced the pricing of the products they sell.

Table 13

Annotated Responses to Research Question 5, Interview Question 1

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	For me, I don't really take note of their economic status because most of the time, my customers are my classmates and since I do not know everyone's economic status in my classmates, I just price it fairly for everyone. Meaning, if I price it 70 pesos for one student, I'll price it 70 pesos for everybody. Now, if we talk about people outside school that I do know the social economic status, for example, my best friend	The respondent spoke calmly while answering the question.

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	<p>who would commission me occasionally for her school projects. Since she is quite well-off, I do price my products slightly higher if not maybe more overpriced compared to my classmates because I do know that she is well-off. So, I do price it a little bit more [<i>sic</i>] higher than my classmates.</p>	
Participant 2	<p>Generally, I try to make my products as cheap as I can make it. And they won't be on par with factory produced since I made it myself. And it is a manpower thing and not a machine thing. So, generally when I try to sell something in the economics [<i>sic</i>], I try to make it as cheap as possible. Since it will lead to my customers buying from me for a longer time. And they won't be discouraged to buy from me since it will be at an affordable price for a student.</p> <p>And I can understand that since I am a student and this is the reason why I am doing it.</p>	<p>The respondent seemed relaxed while answering the question.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Actually ‘pag dito sa school syempre mga students so I make it affordable as possible kasi di naman lahat may malaking baon or malaking pera na meron ayon din kasi yung rule sa business like know your target market. Kasi kung students ang target market my dapat mababa ang price, affordable yung price okay din naman ang quality. Yung sulit ganyan. Sa students. Sa outside the school, pinaprice ko siya ng medyo higher kasi kapag nasa labas kasi ng school grown adults na nabili mayroon na sila mga sariling pera they're more focused on the quality instead of the price. So, syempre kung mataas ang quality dapat mataas din ang price. So ayon yung factors na cinoconsider ko in terms of pricing.</p> <p><i>“Here in school, since they’re students, I make it as affordable as possible because not everyone has a big allowance. That’s also a rule in business: know your target market. If students are your target market, the price should be affordable but the quality should still be good, worth it for students. Outside school, I price</i></p>	<p>The participant displayed composure while answering the question.</p>

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	<i>it a bit higher because most buyers are adults with their own money, and they focus more on quality instead of price. If the quality is high, the price should also be high. Those are the factors I consider in pricing.”</i>	
Participant 4	I don't really base on the economic status of my customers. If they don't have enough budget, I can let them have consideration. But for those that I know, or they would look like the typical customer that has enough budget to buy my products, I mean, I wouldn't lower it or I wouldn't increase the price so that it would be fair.	The participant exhibited some hesitation before answering.
Participant 5	In the past, there were people who sent out questionnaires to the higher [<i>sic</i>] level entrepreneurs. There were questions in their forms asking how much is the daily allowance of the students and how much are they willing to pay for this certain product. I also base it on how much they are actually willing to spend on products like this to mine.	The participant was confident and enthusiastic while answering.

Table 13 presents the responses of the participants to the interview question: *How do you consider the economic status of your customers when you are pricing the goods that you sell?* The table shows that due to the majority of the respondents selling products to fellow students, their prices are adjusted to account for students' limited allowance. Other participants stated that they do not take note of the economic status of customers to practice fairness. However, they noted that for customers with higher budget capabilities, they may increase the price of products. The researchers also observed that the respondents seemed generally calm and collected when answering this question.

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Participant 1 stated that they usually did not take into account the economic status of their customers to impose fairness. However, they noted that for people outside of school whom they may know the economic status of, they may increase the price accordingly. On the other hand, participant 2 emphasizes their effort in trying to make a product as cheap as possible to cater to their target demographic: students with limited allowance. Similarly, participant 3 highlighted the importance of knowing your target market, and stated how they adjusted their prices based on their target demographic. Participant 4 has similar sentiments with participant 1, opting to practice fairness by disregarding customers' economic status. Lastly, participant 5 shared the other participants' outlooks, adding that they also took into account the potential demand of customers when pricing their products.

Thematic Chart M

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“So, generally when I try to sell something in the economics [<i>sic</i>], I try to make it as cheap as possible. Since it will lead to my customers buying from me for a longer time. And they won't be discouraged to buy from me since it will be at an affordable price for a student.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“Actually pag dito sa school syempre mga students so I make it affordable as possible kasi di naman lahat may malaking baon or malaking pera na meron ayon din kasi yung rule sa</p>	<p>Consideration of Student Budget</p>	<p>Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations</p>

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<p>business like know your target market.”</p> <p><i>“Here in school, since they’re students, I make it as affordable as possible because not everyone has a big allowance. That’s also a rule in business: know your target market.”</i> – Participant 3</p> <p>“If they don't have enough budget, I can let them have consideration.” – Participant 4</p> <p>“In the past, there were people who sent out questionnaires to the higher [sic] level entrepreneurs. There were questions in their forms asking how much is the daily allowance of the students and how much are they willing to pay for this certain product.” – Participant 5</p>		
<p>“For example, my best friend who would commission me occasionally for her school projects. Since she is quite well-off, I do price my products slightly higher if not maybe more overpriced compared to my classmates because I do know that she is well-off.” – Participant 1</p> <p>“Sa outside the school, pinaprice ko siya ng medyo higher kasi kapag nasa labas kasi ng school grown adults na nabili mayroon na sila mga sariling pera they're more focused on the quality instead of the price.”</p> <p><i>“Outside school, I price it a bit higher because most buyers are adults with their own money, and they focus more on quality instead of price.”</i> – Participant 3</p>	<p>Price Increase to Outside Customers</p>	
<p>“For me, I don't really take note of their</p>	<p>Principle of Fairness</p>	

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<p>economic status because most of the time, my customers are my classmates and since I do not know everyone's economic status in my classmates, I just price it fairly for everyone. Meaning, if I price it 70 pesos for one student, I'll price it 70 pesos for everybody.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“But for those that I know, or they would look like the typical customer that has enough budget to buy my products, I mean, I wouldn't lower it or I wouldn't increase the price so that it would be fair.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>		
<p>“I also base it on how much they are actually willing to spend on products like this to mine [sic].” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Market Position Awareness</p>	

Thematic Chart M highlights the superordinate theme, ***Ethical Business Practices and Customer relations***, specifically through customer-based pricing. The responses showed that the participants’ maintained prices within the student budget as these are their primary customers. Conversely, those who sell products outside of school premises implemented increased prices due to the less limited nature of their budget. Some participants focused on maintaining consistent pricing to practice fairness. Meanwhile, Participant 5 highlighted their focus on possible customer demand when pricing their products. Evidently, the respondents’ consideration of the customers’ budget, demographic, and demand affect the prices they set for their products.

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The superordinate theme, *Ethical Business Practices and Customer relations*, manifested through subordinate themes such as *consideration of student budget, price increase to outside customers, principle of fairness*, and *market position awareness*. Together, they demonstrate how respondents applied varying pricing based on their customers.

The first subordinate theme, *consideration of student budget*, reveals how the respondents adjusted their prices based on student allowance. The majority of the respondents sold products to fellow students, thereby prompting them to consider what prices are affordable even for those without a high budget. Specifically, Participant 2 highlighted the need to know your target market and adjust your prices accordingly to maximize profit. This is in line with the study of Cakranegara et al. (2022), which stated that product pricing had a positive effect on consumer purchasing interest, as it is closely related to consumer purchasing power, thereby impacting business profitability.

Similarly, the second subordinate theme, *price increase to outside customers*, highlights the respondents' initiative to base their pricing on customer demographic. Participant 1 stated that they increased their prices for customers that they know to be well-off. Meanwhile, Participant 3 stated that they increased their prices when selling to outside customers due to their willingness to pay more for quality products. This behavior is an example of price discrimination, a pricing strategy in which a seller charges different prices for the same product depending on the customers' willingness to pay or other relevant characteristics. In the case of Participant 1, this relevant characteristic is

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the affluence of the customer, with well-off customers receiving marked up prices due to their increased purchasing power (Wang, 2023).

The third subordinate theme, *principle of fairness*, emphasizes how some participants opted to maintain consistent pricing to exercise fairness. Aside from the moral perspective, in entrepreneurship, this practice is often used to build trust with customers, directly affecting their satisfaction (Mushagalusa et al., 2021).

Finally, the fourth subordinate theme, *market position awareness*, shows how a participant adjusted their product pricing based on predicted customer demand. In the field of entrepreneurship, pricing is driven by demand (Zhuo et al., 2024). Sellers consider their target market’s interest before coming up with reasonable prices for upcoming products. Thus, the participant’s consideration of their market position in pricing goods coincides with trends found in relevant literature.

Table 14

Annotated Responses to Research Question 5, Interview Question 2

Participants	Responses	Researcher’s Observation
Participant 1	For me, because my products are mostly art commissions, I do price it based on the effort and the criteria that they provided for the products to be. Like, if the product is to be drawn in an illustration board [<i>sic</i>], I would automatically add a 20 plus addition [<i>sic</i>] in the price for the added material. So, for that, I would price it based on the materials I would use and also the time and effort. But since I am consistent in	The respondent took time to think before answering.

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	<p>the effort and time that I give to a commission in a drawing, I would usually charge it around 100 to 300 pesos depending on the size and the effort of the paper.</p>	
Participant 2	<p>For example, for sweets. Sweets are generally easier to make. But, when I bake something—for example, bread and cinnamon rolls or maybe other baked goods—baking is generally harder than making sweets. So, in terms of not actually quality but I take into account the effort I put in. So, if baking is inherently harder and it takes longer since you have to let the dough sit, you have to bake it, you have to mix it, then I would price it accordingly and I would not cross the threshold of over 100% since it only needs to hang around 50-100% less than [<i>sic</i>]. So, if I sell something for example at 10 pesos, 10 pesos is my raw price without profit. So either I have to increase it either to 15 or to 20, only around that range. I would not exceed over 100% since that would be affecting my customers.</p>	<p>The respondent showed enthusiasm while answering the question.</p>
Participant 3	<p>Syempre, ‘di mawawala diyan yung costing ng ingredients. Wala naman gustong magbenta nang palugi. Costing ‘di mawawala yung labor and ingredients tapos dapat nandoon lahat as in macocompute mo lahat. Kasi kung wala kang computation, ‘di mo alam magkano kikitain mo kung kumikita ka ba or nalulugi ka ba. In business kasi, pinakaimportante talaga yung costing kasi doon ka magbabase sa price. Based sa costing na ‘yon tsaka mo lang siya mapapatungan ng gusto mong kitain.</p> <p><i>“Costing of ingredients is important. No one wants to sell at a loss. You have to compute labor and ingredients, everything. Without computation, you won’t know how much you earn or if you’re losing money. In business, costing is very important because that’s what you base your price on. From that cost, you add your desired profit.”</i></p>	<p>The respondent was calm while answering the question.</p>

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Participant 4	Since my products are handmade, I mean they are quality. They are made with 100% polyester cotton and I use different methods to enhance the product even more. So I can say my product is in its best quality rather than other handmade products that I have made for the past businesses that I have tried to do. So if my products are in its [sic] best quality, I would definitely price them a little bit more than the previous prices. Since it's in good quality, it's reasonable that I have increased the price. If my product is in its low quality version, I would decrease the price so that my customers will buy that product even though it's low quality or not good looking. But since it has a low price, they can have the thought to buy that since it's much cheaper.	The respondent seemed eager to share their answer.
Participant 5	Usually, I try to find cheaper yet high quality materials to make my products. But sometimes, if there's no other option and it's a bit pricey, I will increase the price of my products. But most of the time, I still try to stay within my allotted budget or quota for my products.	The respondent took some time before answering the question.

Table 14 presents the responses of the participants regarding the interview question: *How do you price your goods according to the quality of the products that you sell?* The responses revealed that participants changed their product pricing based on labor, order customization, and material costs. Most participants emphasized the importance of budgeting and profit, highlighting both as essential in maintaining a business. The researchers also observed a general increase in the time taken to answer this particular research question.

Participant 1 stated that they priced their products based on labor and material-costs. This sentiment is echoed by Participant 2, who emphasizes the need to

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take into account the effort put into a product when choosing its price. However, they also showed reluctance to increase their prices by over 100% as consideration for their customers. Participant 3 also highlighted the importance of costing for maintaining a business without losses. Participant 4 noted that their prices were highly dependent on the quality of their products, opting to reduce prices for lower quality goods and increase prices for higher quality items. Finally, Participant 5 shared their experience in trying to find high quality materials with low prices to stay within their allocated budget.

Thematic Chart N

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“So, if I sell something for example at 10 pesos, 10 pesos is my raw price without profit. So either I have to increase it either to 15 or to 20, only around that range. I would not exceed over 100% since that would be affecting my customers.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“But most of the time, I still try to stay within my allotted budget or quota for my products.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	Pricing Strategies	Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations
<p>“For me, because my products are mostly art commissions, I do price it based on the effort and the criteria that they provided for the products to be. [...] So, for that, I would price it based on the materials I would use and also the time and effort.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p>	Cost-Based Pricing	

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<p>“So, in terms of not actually quality but I take into account the effort I put in. So, if baking is inherently harder [...] then I would price it accordingly and I would not cross the threshold of over 100%.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“Syempre, ‘di mawawala diyan yung costing ng ingredients. Wala naman gustong magbenta nang palugi. Costing ‘di mawawala yung labor and ingredients tapos dapat nandoon lahat as in macocompute mo lahat.”</p> <p><i>“Costing of ingredients is important. No one wants to sell at a loss. You have to compute labor and ingredients, everything.”</i> – <i>Participant 3</i></p> <p>“Since my products are handmade, I mean they are quality. They are made with 100% polyester cotton and I use different methods to enhance the product even more. [...] Since it's in good quality, it's reasonable that I have increased the price. If my product is in its low quality version, I would decrease the price so that my customers will buy that product even though it's low quality or not good looking.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p> <p>“Usually, I try to find cheaper yet high quality materials to make my products. But sometimes, if there's no other option and it's a bit pricey, I will increase the price of my products.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>		
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The thematic analysis of Table 28 centers on the superordinate theme ***Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations***, specifically through profit-based business models that showed how participants determined the prices of their products according to

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quality. The data suggests that, despite participants aiming to generate profit through entrepreneurship, product quality remained a key consideration when adjusting prices, with prices decreasing for lower-quality products and increasing for higher-quality products. Quality was determined by the time and effort needed to create a product as well as the cost of the materials used. Most participants emphasized the significance of effort, specifically highlighting the labor-intensive nature of creating products.

Additionally, Participant 2 indicated that a 100% markup was the limit they set for increasing prices, as exceeding this threshold could lessen customer demand—which would lower the profitability of the business. Aside from avoiding unnecessarily high markups, Participant 5 revealed budgeting as a key factor in ensuring the business stays sustainable.

The superordinate theme, *Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations*, manifested through subordinate themes such as *pricing strategies* and *cost-based pricing*. Together, they illustrate how the respondents applied a profit-based business model to balance product quality, labor costs, material costs, and final product costs.

The first subordinate theme, *pricing strategies*, referred to how the participants determined their maximum markup price and the strategies they utilized to manage pricing. In the case of Participant 5, they indicated that they stayed within their allotted budget and product quota to ensure profitability. This behavior aligns with previous studies that identified budgetary control as a significant predictor of financial growth (Cawaling & Natividad, 2021).

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The second subordinate theme, *cost-based pricing*, is defined as the easiest and common method for setting prices, as it is based on financial information related to product cost, which includes considering profit margins (Tahat, 2023). In accordance with this, the thematic analysis described cost-based pricing as the participants' tendency to determine product pricing based on production costs, which included material expenses and the labor, in terms of time and effort involved in creating a product.

Table 15

Annotated Responses to Research Question 5, Interview Question 3

Participants	Responses	Researcher's Observation
Participant 1	Since the considerations is [<i>sic</i>] mainly sometimes based on the economic status of a person, if I do know their economic status, it affects them in a way that sometimes my customers just back out since they know I am also charging them a little bit more than I would usually charge. However, since I try to maintain consistency when I am in school in the pricing, they usually overlook the pricing so they would still achieve their needs in my services.	The respondent took some time to think before responding to the question.
Participant 2	It has a positive effect. Most of my customers are never getting discouraged in buying from me and actually they are looking for it. It has been really unfortunate since I do not have the time to make them and people keep asking for it, which is a good thing. However, I cannot reciprocate these feelings which I will. There's still next year, I'm still gonna be Grade 12 and I will eventually get back to entrepreneurship. Hopefully, when I do get back, my customers will still be there and waiting for my products.	The participant was animated while answering the question. They also used hand gestures to highlight specific points in their

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		response.
Participant 3	<p>Nakakaapekto siya positively kasi alam mo yung kumikita rin ako parang ano siya win-win situation tapos sila makakabili ng product na sulit na. Yeah, makatarunga. Positive naman siya 'di sa pandaraya or what.</p> <p><i>“It affects it positively. I earn, and it’s a win-win situation. They can buy a product that’s worth it and fairly priced. It’s positive, not about deceiving anyone.”</i></p>	The respondent maintained enthusiasm while answering the question.
Participant 4	<p>Since I'm a fellow student to them, I should give consideration on practicality. I don't want them to think that it's too pricey for that specific product. So I'm gonna give discounts, yeah discounts, considerations on lesser price. But I would retain it if I increase the price or I would decrease it more if they have complaints especially. I will accept customer reviews since I'm still a small business. I should probably rely on the customers' tips and my parents' tips also so that I can run my business much more smoothly.</p>	The participant took time to think before answering the question.
Participant 5	<p>So, applying what I considered in their backgrounds, I think it affects my business in a good way. Since my customers are able to get quality products from me that are also affordable and within their budget, I am also receiving enough income. I am satisfied with what I get from my products too.</p>	The participant was smiling and seemed happy to share their answer.

Table 15 shows the responses of the participants to the interview question: *How does applying these considerations affect your self-run business in SRSTHS?* Most of the respondents agreed that these ethical considerations positively affected their businesses. However, some respondents stated that their flexible pricing due to the economic status

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of their customers may cause some clients to be dissuaded from purchasing products. Additionally, the researchers observed some hesitance from the respondents before answering the question. Hand gestures were also repeatedly used to emphasize their points.

Participant 1 stated that the customers have a tendency to back out when they know that their economic status is known and taken advantage of by the seller. However, they also noted that practicing consistency helps build enough trust for them to overlook the pricing. Participant 2 stated that their considerations have had a positive effect on their business by garnering repeat customers. Similarly, Participant 3 also noted a positive effect, describing it as a “win-win situation.” Meanwhile, Participant 4 noted the impact of customer feedback on their pricing decisions. Finally, Participant 5 also agreed that the previous considerations positively affected both their business and their customers by providing income and quality products respectively.

Thematic Chart O

Participants Responses	Subordinate Themes	Superordinate Themes
<p>“But I would retain it if I increase the price or I would decrease it more if they have complaints especially. I will accept customer reviews since I'm still a small business.” – <i>Participant 4</i></p>	Customer Feedback Integration	Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations
<p>“However, since I try to maintain consistency when I am in school in the pricing, they usually</p>	Positive Effect of Pricing	

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<p>overlook the pricing so they would still achieve their needs in my services.” – <i>Participant 1</i></p> <p>“It has a positive effect. Most of my customers are never getting discouraged in buying from me and actually they are looking for it.” – <i>Participant 2</i></p> <p>“Nakakaapekto siya positively kasi alam mo yung kumikita rin ako parang ano siya win-win situation tapos sila makakabili ng product na sulit na.” <i>“It affects it positively. I earn, and it’s a win-win situation. They can buy a product that’s worth it and fairly priced.”</i> – <i>Participant 3</i></p> <p>“...I think it affects my business in a good way. Since my customers are able to get quality products from me that are also affordable and within their budget, I am also receiving enough income.” – <i>Participant 5</i></p>	<p>Considerations</p>	
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Thematic Chart O centers around one core superordinate theme: ***Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations***, specifically through mutually beneficial relationships with customers. The data shows that the respondents’ consideration of the customers has led to positive effects in their business. Notably, the effects of the researchers’ pricing considerations has been described as a “win-win” situation by Participant 3, stating that the seller benefits by earning and the customers benefit by receiving quality products . Overall, the respondents agreed that taking into account customer feedback can induce a

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mutually beneficial relationship with their customers, wherein customers get cheaper prices and the sellers will have an increased number of customers and customer loyalty.

The superordinate theme, *Ethical Business Practices and Customer Relations*, was found through the subordinate themes *customer feedback integration* and *positive effect of pricing considerations*. These subordinate themes explore how respondents integrated customer feedback into their business practices, and how this was able to positively affect their businesses by forming relationships with customers that are advantageous to both parties.

The first subordinate theme, *customer feedback integration*, highlighted how a participant took into account customer suggestions when pricing their products. This corresponds with the study of Xu and Yang (2025) which states that the seller's pricing is largely affected by customer feedback. The respondent's answer reflects the findings in the study, specifically by showing their willingness to decrease prices if customers show negative reactions.

The second subordinate theme, *positive effects of pricing considerations*, explains how the pricing considerations taken by respondents aided in their business ventures. Participants cited customer satisfaction and loyalty as the main benefits of this strategy, stating that customers rarely get discouraged from buying products due to their affordable nature. This is in line with the findings of Ali & Anwar (2021) which found that selling products at an affordable cost to attract customers and build seller reputation had a positive effect on customer behavior. The respondents prioritized building customer

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trust by anchoring their prices to customer budgets and maintaining quality products,
mirroring the findings of the aforementioned study.

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CHAPTER V

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the interpreted and analyzed results of the study.

Summary of Findings

The data gathered from the semi-structured interviews revealed relevant but varying responses from the five (5) participants selected, as expected considering their different experiences with student entrepreneurship. The interview questions and the participants' responses focused on the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School (SRSTHS), with the participants' replies revolving around their motivations for pursuing student entrepreneurship, the different challenges they faced, the factors (perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and social influences) shaping their entrepreneurial intentions, and the ethical considerations taken into account during their entrepreneurial activities. The specific findings of the semi-structured interviews are as follows:

1. All participants experienced conflicting feelings with their engagement in entrepreneurship at Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School. Their responses showed a strong interest in pursuing entrepreneurship, primarily motivated by financial empowerment and increased autonomy. Besides the revenue-related incentives, engagement with customers and the feedback they received also served as motivating factors inspiring the participants to further

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develop and expand their entrepreneurial initiatives. However, their responses later revealed that the need to balance academic, personal, and professional obligations to some extent compromised their academic performance. Yet, the participants still demonstrated a proactive mindset, perceiving these challenges as opportunities for growth.

2. Money was the primary motivation of the participants for pursuing entrepreneurship. Some highlighted the importance of making their own money in gaining financial freedom, enabling them to purchase their wants and go on leisurely activities without the need to ask their parents for money. Additionally, most participants expressed a desire to assist their family's financial situation by taking up entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, some participants also became an entrepreneur out of personal desire and curiosity, as they saw the benefits of doing so. Specifically, one participant pursued entrepreneurship with the expectation that it will give them experiences that they will be able to use in the future.
3. Operational challenges were the primary problems faced by the participants and were classified into five categories: production struggles, customer expectation pressure, scheduling conflicts, publicity and marketing difficulty, and administrative restrictions. Participants expressed difficulties in maintaining a business due to a lack of manpower, as all were self-managed and had to handle production, sales, and financial duties independently. They also faced limited capital, unrecovered investments, and insufficient profits for producing additional

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batches of products. Customer expectations added pressure to the participants to maintain high product quality and avoid negative feedback. One participant revealed the troubles of marketing products while being shy and having limited connections, also highlighting the added challenge of managing a business at a young age due to the split attention between academics and entrepreneurial activities. Additionally, one of the participants noted the role of administrative restrictions in limiting their freedom to sell certain products.

4. Participants revealed that perceived desirability was strongly influenced by the potential benefits of pursuing entrepreneurship. These benefits appeared as improvements in the following: time management, communication skills, and budgeting and financial literacy. Many participants stated that these skill developments also assisted them in academic contexts. They also identified accessibility, environmental factors, initial funding, and prior experiences as primary components influencing the perceived feasibility of entrepreneurship. Social influence from peers, family, and teachers inspired participants to launch and grow their businesses, playing a significant role in their motivation while also providing financial, emotional, and business management guidance. Due to this, perceived feasibility and social influences were found to be linked, as initial support from family and peers—in the form of funding and experience—made starting a business more manageable, thereby enhancing feasibility.
5. All of the participants are affected by ethical considerations when it comes to

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pricing their products. They primarily consider the demographic of their customer, lowering or increasing their prices based on it. Additionally, they take into account the product quality and production cost, minimizing losses while maintaining reasonable prices to sustain customers.

Conclusions

Student entrepreneurship is a challenging pursuit primarily influenced by the desire for financial independence, entrepreneurial curiosity, and real-world experience. Perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and social factors all affect students' tendency to pursue entrepreneurship. The study found that perceived desirability is centered around the belief that student entrepreneurship can assist in skills development. Additionally, perceived feasibility and social factors were found to be linked, as participants stated that support from parents allowed them to gain initial funding and prior experiences that increased their perceived feasibility of student entrepreneurship. Moreover, other factors like accessibility, environment, and teacher attitude contributed to entrepreneurial intention. Becoming a student entrepreneur comes with many challenges, mainly about balancing academics and entrepreneurship. Learning how to deal with these challenges led to the development of various skills in the student entrepreneurs, with an emphasis on time management skills, communication skills, and financial literacy. Thus, student entrepreneurship is a beneficial pursuit for those with perseverance and resources, as it allows students to gain real world experiences, extra finances, and develop skills that they can use in the future.

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Recommendations

Based on the identified limitations and findings of this study, several areas can be further improved in future research. The recommendations are as follows:

1. Students who are looking to get into entrepreneurship may use the findings of this study to understand the advantages and disadvantages of being a student entrepreneur.
2. Student entrepreneurs may refer to the findings of this study to enhance business operations by applying pricing and marketing strategies that the respondents found effective,
3. Anchored in the study's findings, it is recommended that educational institutions like Department of Education (DepEd) mainstream experiential learning in finance, budgeting, and entrepreneurship to effectively strengthen students' financial literacy during adolescence. Since money was found to be a key motivator, these immersive interventions can aid students manage their financial assets ethically and responsibly, grow their resources rather than deplete them, and develop independence acquiring the necessary skills that will prepare them for post-school life.
4. Although this study validated the usage of only five participants, increasing the number of interviewees could reveal additional insights on the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs, thus also improving the generalizability of the findings.

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5. Future studies should test the generalizability of the findings by exploring the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in other academic tracks, as this study was conducted in a Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) school.
6. Future research may study long-term effects of early entrepreneurial exposure on students' career aspirations and entrepreneurial mindset into adulthood.
7. A mixed-method study could be conducted to provide richer and more comprehensive insights, investigating objective measurements and subjective experiences of students' entrepreneurial engagement.

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Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Interview Guide

Introduction

Good day, [Insert name of participant]! First of all, we would like to thank you for your participation in our study as one of our five participants. I am [Insert Name of Interviewer #1] and I am [Insert Name of Interviewer #2] and we will be your interviewers for today. To give you an overview, our study is entitled “Lived Experiences of Student Entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School” and we aim to assess the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs from Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School (SRSTHS).

We strictly ensure the confidentiality of data in order to maintain your safety and privacy in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 under R.A. 10173. Please be informed that at any given time, you are allowed to withdraw from participating in this study. Kindly inform us if this situation arises at any point in this interview.

Preparatory Questions

Before we begin, we want to ensure that you feel at ease throughout the interviewing process. If you are in need of a break at any point during the interview, please do not hesitate to inform us. Do you have any further questions or concerns before we proceed with the interview? If there are none, are you ready to begin?

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
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1. Could you tell us about yourself? (Grade level, age, interests)
2. How long have you been a student entrepreneur?

Research Question	Interview Questions
What are the lived experiences of student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How would you describe your experiences as a student entrepreneur in SRSTHS? 2. In what way has entrepreneurship affected your daily life as a student? 3. Are there times when you tell yourself, “entrepreneurship has made my life easier/harder”? Explain.
What are the different motivations of SRSTHS students for pursuing student entrepreneurship?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What motivates you in being a student entrepreneur? 2. Do these motivations make your life as an entrepreneur easier? How so? 3. For you, how important are these motivations in pursuing entrepreneurship? How significantly do they affect your performance?
What are the different challenges faced by student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As a student entrepreneur, do you face any challenges regarding your businesses? How so? 2. Do these challenges affect your daily life outside of entrepreneurship, for instance, in an academic context? Explain. 3. How were you able to handle these challenges, and were you able to use these hindrances to your advantage? How so?

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<p>How do perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and social influences shape entrepreneurial intention among SRSTHS students?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What made entrepreneurship appealing to you and how did that affect your decision to pursue your own business?2. How did your perception of how achievable entrepreneurship was affect your decision to become an entrepreneur?3. How did different social factors affect your decision to become an entrepreneur?
<p>What are the ethical considerations taken into account by the student entrepreneurs in SRSTHS?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. How do you consider the economic status of your customers when you are pricing the goods that you sell?2. How do you price your goods according to the quality of the products that you sell?3. How does applying these considerations affect your self-run business in SRSTHS?

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Appendix B

Summary of Pre-Survey Results

Preliminary Survey on Student Entrepreneurship in SRSTHS

Survey Item / Category	Number of Respondents (n)	Percentage (%)
Total Number of Respondents	70	100%
Student Entrepreneurs	11	15.7%
Non-Entrepreneurs	59	84.3%
Entrepreneurs Who Sell on School Grounds	8	72.7% of entrepreneurs
Entrepreneurs Who Do Not Sell on School Grounds	3	27.3% of entrepreneurs
Respondents Aware of Student Entrepreneurs in SRSTHS	37	52.9%
Respondents Not Aware of Student Entrepreneurs in SRSTHS	33	47.1%

Note: The survey was conducted among students of Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School (SRSTHS) across Grade 7 to Grade 11. Percentages for entrepreneurs who sell/do not sell on campus are computed relative to the total number of student entrepreneurs (n=11).

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Appendix C

Sample Consent Form

February 5, 2026

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School

Subject: **Consent to Participate in the Research Study**

Dear Student,

Good day!

You are invited to participate in a research study entitled "Lived Experiences of Student Entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School." This study aims to understand the motivations, challenges, and lived experiences of Junior High School students who engage in entrepreneurial activities while managing their academic responsibilities.

Your participation will involve a one-on-one interview where you will be asked questions about your experiences as a student entrepreneur. The interview will take approximately 20-30 minutes. With your permission, the interview may be audio-recorded for accuracy in data collection.

Your participation in this study is **entirely voluntary**. You may choose not to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty or negative consequences.

All information you provide will be treated with **strict confidentiality**. Your identity will not be revealed in any part of the study, and your responses will only be used for academic and research purposes.

There are no known risks involved in participating in this study. While there is no direct monetary benefit, your participation will help contribute to a better understanding of student entrepreneurship in SRSTHS and may benefit future students, teachers, and researchers.

Respectfully yours,

Kian Gabriel E. Arambulo

Gabrielle C. Basan

Shendelzare M. Capote

Tia B. Chen

Jhoen Leo B. De Paz

Daesha S. Doculara

Yagoh Nrke D. Manaog
Student-Researchers

Response Slip

Please check (✓) one:

- I AGREE to participate in the research study described above.
- I DO NOT AGREE to participate in the research study.

Student's Name (Printed): _____

Grade & Section: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

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Appendix D

Validation Sheet

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF SANTA ROSA CITY
SANTA ROSA SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY HIGH SCHOOL
LM Subd., Brgy. Market Area, City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

INTERVIEW GUIDE VALIDATION SHEET

Research Title: *Lived Experiences of Student Entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School*

Check the attached semi-structured interview guide and tick the column which fit your evaluation.

Indicators	Yes	No
Ethical Consideration		
1. Introduction allows the researcher/s to introduce themselves and their study.	✓	
2. The purpose of the study is stated well.	✓	
3. The 'confidentiality clause' is communicated.	✓	
4. The 'informed consent' is included.	✓	
5. The duration and flow of the interview is announced.	✓	
Interview Questions		
6. Questions are aligned and appropriate for the study.	✓	
7. Questions allow storytelling or narration of experiences.	✓	
8. Questions are open-ended questions.	✓	
9. Questions are short and can easily be understood.	✓	
10. Questions are positively stated.	✓	
11. Questions are clear, precise, and use simple words.	✓	
12. Questions are in polite and courteous tones.	✓	
13. Questions are focused on gathering data through lived experiences and not opinion.	✓	
14. Questions are adequate for every research questions.	✓	
15. Questions are not leading, discriminative and bias.	✓	
16. Questions are sequenced to allow smooth flow of ideas.	✓	
17. Questions are grammatically correct.	✓	
18. Questions suit the level of the identified participants.	✓	

Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Appendix-A-Interview-Questions-Validation-Sheet-Fig1-348609149-Invested-4-May-2023-Modified>

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Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF SANTA ROSA CITY
SANTA ROSA SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY HIGH SCHOOL
LM Subd., Brgy. Market Area, City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Rating: 16-18 checks: Very Satisfactory 10-12 checks: Unsatisfactory
 13-15 checks: Satisfactory Below 10 checks: Very Unsatisfactory

Remarks: _____

Recommendation: _____

Evaluated by:

EMERITA BANSAN
Signature over printed name
CPA / PARTNER
Profession/ Degree/ Work Position
LAYUC REANO & ASSOCIATES
Affiliation
24 FEB 2020
Date

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ENERITO M. CLIMA, PhD
Master Teacher II

Approved by:
SYLVIA L. MARQUEZ, EdD
Principal IV

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research study entitled **“Lived Experiences of Student Entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School”** performed and conducted by **Arambulo, Kian Gabriel E., Manaog, Yagoh Nrke D., Capote, Shendelzare M., De Paz, Jhoen Leo B., Doculara, Daesha S., Basan, Gabrielle C., and Chen, Tia A.**, of Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School, Santa Rosa City Laguna, had undergone the process of research instrument validation with the undersigned. The said process had made for the validity of the instruments as well as the data to be collected which are needed for this research study.

This also certifies that the above-mentioned names have conducted discussions with the undersigned to address and correct errors that have been identified during the validation.

This certification is issued on the 24th day of February, year 2026 at Santa Rosa City, Laguna upon the request of the aforementioned personage. Thus, **VALID FOR RESEARCH PURPOSES ONLY.**

EMELITA BASAN PARTNER - CPA
HRA
Validator

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
 LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
 REGION IV-A CALABARZON
 SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF SANTA ROSA CITY
 SANTA ROSA SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY HIGH SCHOOL
 LM Subd., Brgy. Market Area, City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

INTERVIEW GUIDE VALIDATION SHEET

Research Title: Lived Experiences of Student Entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School

Check the attached semi-structured interview guide and **tick** the column which fit your evaluation.

Indicators	Yes	No
Ethical Consideration		
1. Introduction allows the researcher/s to introduce themselves and their study.	✓	
2. The purpose of the study is stated well.	✓	
3. The 'confidentiality clause' is communicated.	✓	
4. The 'informed consent' is included.	✓	
5. The duration and flow of the interview is announced.	✓	
Interview Questions		
6. Questions are aligned and appropriate for the study.	✓	
7. Questions allow storytelling or narration of experiences.	✓	
8. Questions are open-ended questions.	✓	
9. Questions are short and can easily be understood.	✓	
10. Questions are positively stated.	✓	
11. Questions are clear, precise, and use simple words.	✓	
12. Questions are in polite and courteous tones.	✓	
13. Questions are focused on gathering data through lived experiences and not opinion.	✓	
14. Questions are adequate for every research questions.	✓	
15. Questions are not leading, discriminative and bias.	✓	
16. Questions are sequenced to allow smooth flow of ideas.	✓	
17. Questions are grammatically correct.	✓	
18. Questions suit the level of the identified participants.	✓	

Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Appendix-A-Interview-Questions-Validation-Sheet-Fig1-348699149> accessed 4 May, 2023. Modified

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 13-15 checks: Satisfactory Below 10 checks: Very Unsatisfactory

Remarks:

This paper underwent content validation and plagiarism screening. The plagiarism check returned a similarity index of 19%, which falls within the acceptable range of 15–20%, manuscript falls within acceptable similarity standards. Several grammatical errors were identified throughout the paper and are recommended for revision. Additionally, some in-text citations do not appear in the bibliography, and some references listed in the bibliography are not cited in the text; these inconsistencies should be corrected for consistency.

Recommendation: _____

Evaluated by:

J. Labini

JOHN RAFAEL C. LABINI

Signature over printed name

MAEd General Science UP-Diliman, Science and Research Teacher
at Southville 5A Integrated National High School

Profession/ Degree/ Work Position

SySTEM Upgrade: Innovative Approaches in STEM Education, Vice
President A.Y. 2023-2024 University of the Philippines-Diliman

Affiliation

February 24, 2026

Date

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Master Teacher II

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Principal IV

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research study entitled “**Lived Experiences of Student Entrepreneurs in Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School**” performed and conducted by **Arambulo, Kian Gabriel E., Manaog, Yagoh Nrke D., Capote, Shendelzare M., De Paz, Jhoen Leo B., Doculara, Daesha S., Basan, Gabrielle C., and Chen, Tia A.**, of Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School, Santa Rosa City Laguna, had undergone the process of research instrument validation with the undersigned. The said process had made for the validity of the instruments as well as the data to be collected which are needed for this research study.

This also certifies that the above-mentioned names have conducted discussions with the undersigned to address and correct errors that have been identified during the validation.

This certification is issued on the 24th day of February, year 2026 at Santa Rosa City, Laguna upon the request of the aforementioned personage. Thus, **VALID FOR RESEARCH PURPOSES ONLY.**

JOHN RAFAEL C. LABINI, LPT

Validator

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Appendix E

Interview Documentation

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Appendix F

Curriculum Vitae

Name: Arambulo, Kian Gabriel E.

Age: 16

Birthday: May 28, 2009

Address: 211 Rizal Blvd., Brgy. Tagapo, Santa Rosa,
Laguna 4026

Sex: Male

Contact Number: 09296646300

Email Address: kian@arambuloworks.com

Motto: “If you’re going through hell, keep going.”

Educational Background and Achievements

- **Division Science and Technology Fair, 2025 – 1st Place**

Skills

- Knowledgeable of the **APA 7th Edition citation format**
- Ability to use **data analysis software**

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Name: Basan, Gabrielle C.

Age: 16

Birthday: June 27, 2009

Address: Block 9 Lot 8, Rosewood Homes, Tagapo,
Santa Rosa, Laguna

Sex: Female

Contact Number: 09276123069

Email Address: gabbasan27@gmail.com

Motto: “Everything will pass.”

Educational Background and Achievements

- **Division Schools Press Conference, 2025** – Participant
- **Hongkong International Science Olympiad, 2024** – Silver Awardee

Skills

- **Data interpretation and discussion**
- **Knowledge of the APA 7th edition citing format**

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Name: Capote, Shendelzare M.

Age: 18

Birthday: November 17, 2007

Address: Block 2 Lot 2, Mangosteen Street, Brgy.
Pacita 2, City of San Pedro, Laguna

Sex: Female

Contact Number: 09946721569

Email Address: shendelzarecapote@gmail.com

Motto: “If we live fast, let us die young.”

Educational Background and Achievements

- **Reconfigured Regional Schools Press Conference, 2026** – Top 40
- **Division Schools Press Conference, 2025** – 1st Place

Skills

- Possesses **people skills** and can work comfortably and efficiently with a team
- Knowledgeable in **research methodologies**, including data collection, analysis, and interpretation

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Name: Chen, Tia A.

Age: 17

Birthday: September 06, 2008

Address: Block 9 Lot 25, Paradise Street, St. Francis
7, Brgy. San Antonio, City of Biñan, Laguna

Sex: Female

Contact Number: 0968 280 4650

Email Address: ctia0968@gmail.com

Motto: “Carpe Diem.”

Educational Background and Achievements

- **Analog Devices Academe Expo, 2025** – 1st Runner Up
- **Regional Science and Technology Fair, 2025** – 2nd Place
- **Division Schools Press Conference, 2025** – 4th Place

Skills

- Interpersonal **communication** skills
- **Data gathering** and **analytical** skills

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Name: De Paz, Jhoen Leo B.

Age: 17

Birthday: September 15, 2008

Address: Block 13, Lot 26, Nile Street, Grand
Riverstone Village, Calamba, Laguna

Sex: Male

Contact Number: 09074181847

Email Address: leodepaz0316@gmail.com

Motto: “Hangga’t may baon, babangon.”

Educational Background and Achievements

- Junior High School Completer

Skills

- Vocational Listener

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Name: Doculara, Daesha S.

Age: 18

Birthday: February 28, 2008

Address: Block 15 Lot 3 Phase 2 Cattleya St.,
Garden Villas 3, Brgy. Malusak, Santa Rosa City,
Laguna

Sex: Female

Contact Number: 09947455857

Email Address: daeshadoculara@gmail.com

Motto: “Your worth is not your output.”

Educational Background and Achievements

- **Consistent with honor**

Skills

- **Methodical** investigation
- Interpersonal **communication** skills

Santa Rosa Science and Technology High School
LM Subdivision, Market Area, City of Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Name: Manaog, Yagoh Nrke D.

Age: 17

Birthday: November 19, 2008

Address: Block 29 Lot 46 Cedar St. Grand Chestnut
Grove, Brgy. Pulong Sta. Cruz Santa Rosa City,
Laguna

Sex: Male

Contact Number: 09093257558

Email Address: manaogyagoh@gmail.com

Motto: "What's done is done."

Educational Background and Achievements

- **Consistent with honor**

Skills

- **Data gathering and interpretation skills**